

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

**Deliverable 6.4 – Re-definition of Learning Outcomes for a
Successful Industrial and Entrepreneurial Career**

Date: May 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA InnoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and Common Research strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	6.4
Work Package:	6
Task:	6.5, 6.6
Lead beneficiary:	Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
Due date of deliverable:	M36 (31 May 2024)
Actual submission date:	30 May 2024
Dissemination level:	Public

Document history

V	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
1	2024-04-25	BME	First draft prepared
2	2024-05-27	UPB	1 st Quality check review
3	2024-05-24	UPM	2 nd Quality check review

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
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2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EELISA InnoCORE Work Package 6 (WP6) primarily deals with reinforcing the cooperation in research and innovation with other sectors, especially with respect to the academia-business cooperation. Based on the discussion on InnoCORE level, recommendations are given for the governances of these structures, that shall be again reviewed and finetuned during implementation.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Dr Ágnes DUDÁS industrial property expert and her team at BME's Technology Transfer Office for conducting and evaluating the surveys about technology transfer practices of the partner universities.

Also thanks to all participating colleagues from the partner universities' technology transfer offices for presentations at the EELISA InnoCORE Technology Transfer Workshop on 10 April 2024, organised by the WP6 Team and local practices sent for this deliverable.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Review and quality check by EELISA

To guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the EELISA office has been consulted for the production of this deliverable.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(in alphabetical order)

Apprenticeship. ‘Apprenticeship is a system for training practitioners of a profession with combination of on-the-job training and academic studies. Large portion of the practical training is conducted during working at host organization’ (Kaczmarek, 2018)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

EIT. The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) is an EU body created by the European Union in 2008 to strengthen Europe’s ability to innovate. The EIT is an integral part of Horizon Europe, the EU’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

Entrepreneurship-focused internship. The entrepreneurship dimension of an internship refers to the opportunities and experiences related to entrepreneurship that an intern may encounter during their internship. It involves fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and developing entrepreneurial skills and knowledge.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Industrial PhD. It is a doctoral programme in which research is carried out in strong collaboration with the industry (sometimes under a co-supervision scheme) where the research results are close to industrial utilization based on pre-drafted IP rights and financing agreements.

Internship. ‘An internship is an instrument to offer a concrete work experience to individuals who are either newly entering or re-entering the labor market, by putting learning at the center, giving them the opportunity of finding their professional field(s) of interest(s) and enhancing their employability. It is conducted either for academic purposes and/or for professional development during a limited time period. It is organized in advance to provide structured learning through practical

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experience and leads to the recognition of learning outcomes, under the supervision of a professional with a significant background in the field of the experience. Aimed at increasing learner's competences and obtaining skills relevant for the labor market, it consists of activities that are connected with the area of study or professional development. Internships may cover: student or graduate placements in companies; practical work-experience oriented projects, traineeship and other relevant activities.' (Kaczmarek, 2018)

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research-focused internship. The research dimension of an internship involves conducting research on a specific topic related to the field or industry in which the internship is taking place.

Traineeship. Traineeship is the general summary term of professional training programmes, including internships and apprenticeships.

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1 Aims and scope

EELISA InnoCORE WP6 primarily deals with reinforcing the cooperation in research and innovation with other sectors, especially with respect to the academia-business cooperation. The main objectives are as follows:

- to reinforce research and innovation dimension of the universities via the concept of Science Parks;
- to meet the transformative challenge of reshaping university operations to provide services for industrial, economical and societal development;
- to construct a dynamic university innovation ecosystem among the consortium members.

The WP consist of eight subtasks as listed in Table 1.

Table 1. EELISA Innocore WP6 tasks

Task#	Task title
6.1	Strengthening resources for technology transfer within the EELISA network
6.2	Developing PhD thesis financed by industry and co-advised
6.3	Creation of Science Park development model - Structural development model
6.4	Models for collaboration with business and industry
6.5	RDI collaboration and answering the societal challenges
6.6	Novel education programs for flexible RDI –a path towards entrepreneurial university

Objectives of the deliverable

The current report deals with tasks *6.4 Models for collaboration with business and industry* and *6.6 Novel Education Programs for Flexible RDI – Path Towards Entrepreneurial University*.

In the current deliverable the reference of EELISA means EELISA 1.0 phase.

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2 Introduction and Preliminary Work

The current deliverable consists of two parts. The first part extends the learning outcomes of the European Engineer Profile, incorporating aspects aimed at enhancing successful industrial and entrepreneurial careers. This section places special emphasis on EELISA-level cooperation, ensuring that the updated outcomes align with the collaborative goals of the EELISA network. The second part involves a comprehensive review of the technology transfer processes at partner universities, proposing a development framework for EELISA-level collaboration. This framework is designed to improve the integration of higher educational learning outcomes into industry and entrepreneurship, facilitating a more seamless transition from academic achievements to practical, professional applications.

Learning outcomes in higher education describe the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes students should acquire upon completing a course or program. These outcomes guide curriculum design, instructional delivery, assessment practices, and student evaluation, ensuring quality education and clear measurement of student achievement. At a European level, the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) harmonizes these outcomes to promote mobility, quality assurance, and employability, using frameworks like the Tuning Project and the European Qualifications Framework (EQF). Additionally, the importance of entrepreneurship is highlighted through its economic impact, with entrepreneurial education fostering key skills such as motivation, opportunity identification, risk management, and networking. Entrepreneurial programs aim to develop creative thinking, innovation, problem-solving, and business acumen, with a strong focus on integrating new technologies and modern business models. The European Commission emphasizes the need for more academically educated entrepreneurs, as formal education can profoundly influence students' entrepreneurial abilities and motivations.

Several related works have been carried out in the course of the EELISA project so far. These have been summarised below.

2.1 UNFOLDS Project

The UNFOLDS project, part of the EELISA initiative, aims to spearhead the transformation of higher education institutions (HEIs) into pivotal contributors to the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem. Through a series of strategic actions, UNFOLDS endeavors to enhance the entrepreneurial landscape within HEIs by implementing innovative approaches. Key outcomes of the project include the development of a Student Engagement Methodological Toolkit, geared towards amplifying students' involvement in entrepreneurial activities within HEIs. Additionally, the project introduces Innovation Co-creation and Stakeholders Involvement Guidelines, focusing on fostering innovation and collaboration among stakeholders through start-up creation and venture building for spin-offs. A Mentorship Program is also established to facilitate HEIs' engagement with the entrepreneurial ecosystem, promoting the co-creation of high-impact social and economic opportunities. Furthermore, the project provides Guidelines for Startup Creation, Venture Builders, and Technology Transfer Programs, offering frameworks for fostering innovation and entrepreneurship within HEIs. To support these endeavors, the project introduces a range of resources and tools for innovation and entrepreneurship, equipping students, researchers, and staff with essential skills and knowledge. Additionally, the project pioneers the launch of a Credentialing System, aimed at recording entrepreneurial activities for students, researchers, and staff, providing recognition and validation of their entrepreneurial endeavors. Through collaborative efforts and innovative initiatives, the UNFOLDS project strives to redefine learning outcomes for a successful

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industrial and entrepreneurial career, laying the groundwork for a dynamic and thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem within HEIs.

EELISA UNFOLDS is set to become a leading European initiative in the transformation of higher education institutions (HEIs) to key players in the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem by means of actions on:

- innovative student engagement activities;
- new collaborations with external partners looking for cocreation of high-impact social and economic opportunities;
- enhanced structures for creating start-ups and venture builders for spin-offs;
- specific programmes for innovation-driven research;
- the development of an entrepreneurial curricula based on credentials;
- the development of advanced training and mentoring schemes.

The UNFOLDS project has yielded several significant outcomes aimed at enhancing the entrepreneurial ecosystem within higher education institutions (HEIs). These outcomes include:

- Student Engagement Methodological Toolkit: A comprehensive toolkit designed to amplify students' involvement in entrepreneurial activities within HEIs, thereby enhancing the scale and scope of their engagement.
- Innovation Co-creation and Stakeholders Involvement Guidelines: Launching new structures and programs focused on start-up creation and venture building for spin-offs, fostering innovation and collaboration among stakeholders.
- Mentorship Program: A mentorship program aimed at increasing HEIs' engagement with the entrepreneurial ecosystem, facilitating the co-creation of high-impact social and economic opportunities and new ventures.
- Guidelines for Startup Creation, Venture Builders, and Technology Transfer Programs: Providing guidelines and frameworks for the establishment of start-ups, venture builders for spin-offs, and technology transfer programs within HEIs, fostering innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Development and Deployment of Innovation and Entrepreneurship Resources: Introduction of resources and tools to support innovation and entrepreneurship within HEIs, equipping students, researchers, and staff with the necessary skills and knowledge.
- Launching of a Credentialing System: Introduction of a credentialing system to record entrepreneurial activities for students, researchers, and staff, providing recognition and validation of their entrepreneurial endeavors.

2.2 EELISA WP2

The preliminary work conducted within EELISA's Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on defining the learning outcomes for the future European Engineer, aligning with the ENAEE guidelines while also incorporating new competencies essential for engineers of the future. These new competencies include ethics and empathy, leadership, and communication skills, emphasizing their importance within the evolving landscape of engineering. The aim is to develop a European Engineer Profile (EEP) that encompasses scientific, technical, and relational outcomes, reflecting the European context of diversity and mobility. The proposed EELISA-EEP is intended to serve as a framework for learning outcomes for future joint degrees, as well as for the EELISA Supplement and Credentials. It builds upon existing frameworks such as the EUR-ACE® Framework Standards and Guidelines and the Washington Accord Graduate Attribute Profile, with additions to emphasize mobility and the European dimension. The EELISA-EEP consists of four conceptual fields: Scientific and theoretical

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knowledge, Addressing sustainability, Interculturalism, and Business and communication skills. These fields aim to equip engineers with the necessary expertise to address real-world challenges while considering social objectives, ethical responsibilities, and sustainability issues. The proposition for the European engineer profile emphasizes competencies that transcend technical specialization and respond to societal demands, aligning with the aspirations of students and the requirements of employers. The preliminary version of the competencies outlined in this proposition is subject to further refinement and adaptation as training courses develop in the coming years, with a focus on lifelong learning and continuous skill development to keep pace with technological advancements and evolving societal needs.

2.3 EELISA WP6

The preliminary work in EELISA WP6 focuses on extending the EELISA internship system to an international level by leveraging existing institutional structures and practices among partners. Rather than creating new structures, the emphasis is on connecting and coordinating existing ones. This entails establishing a "Virtual" Central Office using online tools to facilitate communication and collaboration. The office comprises three units:

EELISA Institutional Internship Coordinators (EELISA IIC): This group, composed of nominated delegates from partner institutions, coordinates communication, collects internship information, develops common procedures, and provides support for staff and interns.

Information Hub: Responsible for developing and maintaining an internship portal, this unit publishes internship offers, supports internship procedures, disseminates information, and promotes activities.

Dissemination Unit: This unit creates support documents, training materials, and organizes workshops for staff and interns, closely collaborating with the EELISA Communication Office and other relevant entities.

At the macro level, the EELISA Apprenticeship and Training Office, especially the IIC group, reports to the Executive Board and the EELISA Office. The Executive Board, Academic and Scientific Board, and Employment Committee play advisory roles in guiding the internship program and ensuring alignment with educational, scientific, and employability objectives.

2.4 INNOCORE WP7

The EELISA InnoCORE WP7 is focused on the "EELISA entrepreneurship action plan," aiming to broaden entrepreneurial activities across EELISA to various target groups. This plan includes two main tasks: establishing a network of business incubators across EELISA and implementing a startup initiative. These tasks are based on three pillars:

- **EELISA Landscape of Startup Support:** This pillar involves mapping key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at each partner institution across the startup journey's stages. The goal is to identify existing resources and potential areas for future collaboration.
- **Sharing Key Startup Support Resources:** This pillar focuses on sharing identified resources among EELISA partners. It includes interlinking resources, promoting activities through media channels and community platforms, and fostering discussions and joint events to enhance collaboration.
- **Implementation of an EELISA-Wide Startup Initiative:** The third pillar outlines plans for a startup initiative between June 2023 and May 2024. This initiative aims to open existing

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resources to all EELISA partners, organize joint events like boot camps and workshops, and host a startup contest. The goal is to support startups in their journey to market entry, leveraging EELISA's diverse expertise and resources.

- The plan emphasizes collaboration, resource sharing, and targeted initiatives to enhance support for startups and founders within the EELISA consortium.

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3 Learning Outcomes for a Successful Industrial and Entrepreneurial Career

According to AHELO – (Assessment of Higher Education Learning Outcomes by OECD), learning outcomes are statements of what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to demonstrate after completion of learning. In the following use the European Engineer Profile (EEP) of the EELISA Alliance as a basis, in which higher education learning outcomes of the European Engineer have been defined. This chapter is an extension to re-define these learning outcomes for a Successful Industrial and Entrepreneurial Career. Items of hard and soft skills are as follows:

Scientific and Theoretical Knowledge

Young engineers can significantly benefit from scientific and theoretical knowledge for their industrial and entrepreneurial careers in several ways:

1. **Problem-solving:** Scientific and theoretical knowledge provides young engineers with a solid foundation for understanding fundamental principles and concepts. This enables them to analyze complex problems critically, identify innovative solutions, and address challenges effectively in both industrial and entrepreneurial settings.
2. **Innovation:** Scientific knowledge often serves as the basis for technological advancements and innovations. By understanding the underlying scientific principles, young engineers can develop new products, processes, and technologies that have the potential to disrupt industries or create entirely new markets, driving entrepreneurial success.
3. **Critical Thinking:** Theoretical knowledge fosters critical thinking skills, allowing young engineers to evaluate existing systems, processes, and methodologies critically. This analytical mindset enables them to identify inefficiencies, areas for improvement, and opportunities for innovation, essential for success in industrial optimization and entrepreneurial ventures.
4. **Adaptability:** A strong grasp of scientific and theoretical concepts equips young engineers with a versatile skill set that can be applied across different industries and sectors. This adaptability enables them to pivot quickly in response to changing market demands, technological advancements, or unexpected challenges, essential qualities for thriving in dynamic industrial and entrepreneurial environments.
5. **Foundation for Research and Development:** Scientific and theoretical knowledge provides a solid foundation for conducting research and development activities. Whether young engineers are exploring new technologies, refining existing products, or optimizing processes, their understanding of fundamental principles guides their experimentation, innovation, and problem-solving efforts.
6. **Risk Management:** Entrepreneurial endeavors inherently involve risk, but scientific and theoretical knowledge empowers young engineers to make informed decisions and mitigate risks effectively. By leveraging their understanding of scientific principles, they can assess the feasibility of new ideas, evaluate potential challenges, and develop strategies to minimize risks associated with technological development or market uncertainty.

As the EELISA alliance offers students the opportunity of exchanging ideas and experiences among partner universities, interculturalism is a part of the benefits EELISA offers to the European Engineer, that is ready for the industrial and entrepreneurial career.

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Interculturalism

Young engineers can significantly benefit from interculturalism in their industrial and entrepreneurial careers in several ways:

1. **Global Market Understanding:** Intercultural competence allows young engineers to understand and navigate diverse cultural nuances within global markets. This understanding is invaluable for developing products and services that resonate with international consumers, effectively targeting diverse customer segments, and adapting business strategies to different cultural contexts.
2. **Cross-Cultural Communication:** Effective communication is essential in industrial and entrepreneurial settings. Intercultural competence enables young engineers to communicate fluently and respectfully across cultural boundaries, fostering strong relationships with clients, partners, and colleagues from diverse backgrounds. This skill facilitates collaboration, negotiation, and conflict resolution, enhancing teamwork and productivity in multicultural environments.
3. **Innovative Thinking:** Exposure to diverse cultural perspectives stimulates innovative thinking and creative problem-solving among young engineers. By engaging with individuals from different cultural backgrounds, students gain new insights, challenge conventional assumptions, and develop innovative solutions to complex challenges. This diversity of thought fuels entrepreneurship by inspiring novel business ideas and strategies that cater to diverse market needs.
4. **Cultural Sensitivity:** Intercultural competence fosters cultural sensitivity and empathy, enabling young engineers to recognize and respect cultural differences while avoiding cultural misunderstandings or stereotypes. This sensitivity is essential for building trust, fostering inclusive workplaces, and promoting diversity and inclusion initiatives within industrial organizations and entrepreneurial ventures.
5. **Adaptability and Flexibility:** In today's globalized world, industries and markets are constantly evolving. Intercultural competence equips young engineers with the adaptability and flexibility needed to thrive in dynamic and multicultural environments. By embracing change and learning from diverse experiences, students can quickly adjust to new situations, seize emerging opportunities, and navigate challenges with resilience and agility.
6. **International Networking:** Intercultural competence facilitates the development of international professional networks, connecting young engineers with industry leaders, mentors, and potential collaborators from around the world. These diverse networks provide access to new markets, funding opportunities, and mentorship resources, accelerating career growth and entrepreneurial success.

Generally, participating in the EELISA alliance, intercultural competence is a vital skill set for young engineers pursuing industrial and entrepreneurial careers in today's interconnected world. By embracing diversity, fostering cross-cultural understanding, and leveraging cultural differences as strengths, students can unlock new opportunities, drive innovation, and make a positive impact on a global scale.

In higher education, the alignment between learning outcomes and their assessment methods is crucial, particularly concerning skills in entrepreneurship and industry readiness. Learning outcomes related to entrepreneurship often encompass a range of competencies, including critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and adaptability, essential for success in dynamic industrial environments. Assessing these outcomes requires innovative assessment methods that go beyond

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traditional exams and essays, such as case studies, business simulations, project-based assessments, and entrepreneurial pitch presentations. These methods not only evaluate students' theoretical knowledge but also their ability to apply concepts in real-world scenarios, develop viable business plans, and communicate their ideas effectively. By aligning assessment methods with learning outcomes, higher education institutions can ensure that students acquire the practical skills and competencies necessary to thrive in entrepreneurial ventures and meet the demands of the industry effectively.

Figure 1. Marching of knowledge assessment to learning outcomes

Entrepreneurship education plays a pivotal role in cultivating entrepreneurial characteristics among students, fostering motivation, and honing skills vital for success in the business world. Through entrepreneurship education, students learn to identify opportunities, navigate risk and uncertainty, and develop the ability to network effectively. The emphasis on international connections within programs like the EELISA alliance of European universities broadens students' perspectives and exposes them to diverse business environments. Events and common courses offered in online or hybrid formats facilitate collaborative learning and provide practical insights into entrepreneurship. Ultimately, the result of entrepreneurial education is the transformation of students' entrepreneurial characteristics, equipping them with the mindset, skills, and networks necessary to thrive in entrepreneurial ventures and contribute meaningfully to the global business landscape.

Figure 2. Flowchart of entrepreneurial development through organised education

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3.1 The Table of Learning Outcomes (EELISA WP2 D2.7) Extended with Entrepreneurial and Industrial Skills

In the table below the European Engineer Profile elaborated in EELISA WP2 (D2.7) has been extended for industrial and entrepreneurial career optimisation.

	Comments	European Engineer profile	Industrial and Entrepreneurial Extension
Knowledge and Understanding	<p>A sound training in the basic sciences is required and must be common to all engineers, whatever their specialization will be. This strong scientific knowledge beyond the scope of the specialization is necessary to allow connection with other disciplines and multidisciplinary collaboration. Mathematics and physics in particular bring rigor in reasoning that allows to go beyond empirical observations by introducing the scientific method. Chemistry, biology, earth science bring multidisciplinary knowledge.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in-depth knowledge and understanding of mathematics, natural sciences and computing sciences underlying the engineering fundamentals, at a level necessary to achieve their application in their engineering specialization as well as collaboration at the interface between different fields. • in-depth knowledge and understanding of engineering disciplines underlying their specialization, at a level necessary to achieve their professional use; • critical awareness of the forefront of their specialisation; • ability to address complex multidisciplinary engineering problems. 	<p>To extend these learning outcomes for a career that not only encompasses industrial prowess but also entrepreneurial success, consider the following additions that emphasize skills in innovation, management, and adaptability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial Skills and Mindset: Engineers should cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset that includes the ability to identify market needs and opportunities. This includes training in the basics of business management, finance, and marketing, allowing them to understand and leverage the commercial aspects of engineering innovations. • Leadership and Project Management: Developing

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			<p>skills in leadership and effective project management, including the ability to plan, organize, direct, and control resources efficiently. This is crucial for leading projects and teams, managing budgets, and delivering results within the constraints of time and money.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation and Design Thinking: Encouragement to engage in continuous innovation and the application of design thinking principles. This involves empathetic approaches to problem-solving that are user-centered and encourage creative solutions to complex problems, fostering an environment where innovation can thrive. Interpersonal and Communication Skills: Proficiency in communication is vital, including the ability to articulate complex ideas clearly and persuasively to a variety of stakeholders, from
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			<p>technical team members to non-technical clients or investors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifelong Learning and Adaptability: Promoting the importance of lifelong learning to stay abreast of emerging technologies and industry trends. This includes the ability to adapt to new tools, technologies, and methodologies, which are crucial in a rapidly changing global landscape. • Global and Cultural Awareness: Understanding global issues and cultural differences that can influence engineering practices and business operations. This awareness is critical for working effectively in multinational teams and succeeding in global markets.
<p>Engineering analysis</p>	<p>The WA agreement insists on the global holistic approach: WA2: Identify, formulate, research literature and analyze <i>complex</i> engineering problems reaching</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to identify and analyse new and complex engineering problems; • ability to select and apply the most appropriate and relevant methods from established analytical, computational and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of Technological and Business Innovation: Engineers should be trained to integrate engineering solutions with business strategies. This includes

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	<p>substantiated conclusions using first principles of mathematics, natural sciences and engineering sciences with holistic considerations for sustainable development* (WK1 to WK4)</p>	<p>experimental methods or new and innovative methods; to critically interpret the outcomes of such analyses;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to conceptualise engineering products, processes and systems; • ability to formulate judgements with incomplete or limited information, <i>that include multidisciplinary approach as well as reflecting on social and ethical responsibilities.</i> • integrate knowledge and handle complexity. • ability to identify, formulate and solve unfamiliar complex engineering problems that are incompletely defined. 	<p>understanding how technological advancements can lead to competitive advantage, market expansion, and improved business models. Training in technology commercialization, from intellectual property management to startup strategies, is crucial.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability and Environmental Impact Assessment: Develop the ability to design and implement solutions that consider not only economic and technical criteria but also sustainability. This involves mastering environmental impact assessments, life-cycle analysis, and sustainable resource management to minimize environmental footprints. • Risk Management and Resilience Planning: Skills in identifying, analyzing, and mitigating risks
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			<p>associated with engineering practices.</p> <p>Understanding the principles of resilience planning to ensure systems and structures are robust against various types of disruptions, whether environmental, economic, or technological.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Data Analytics and Digital Competence: Proficiency in data analytics and the use of cutting-edge digital tools, such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and blockchain technologies, to optimize engineering processes and innovations. This competence is essential for making informed decisions based on large volumes of complex data. • Cross-Cultural Competence and Global Collaboration: Preparation for working in and leading diverse, international
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			<p>teams. This includes cultural competence training to effectively manage and negotiate across cultural boundaries, essential for global project management and international business.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial Finance and Funding Mechanisms: Knowledge of financial principles and funding mechanisms that support innovation, including venture capital, government grants, and crowdfunding. This is vital for engineers looking to launch startups or introduce new products to the market. • Communication and Stakeholder Engagement: Enhanced skills in communicating technical and non-technical aspects of engineering projects to a diverse range of stakeholders, including investors, policymakers,
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			and the public. This also includes the ability to advocate for and explain the benefits of engineering solutions in community and legislative settings.
Engineering design	<p>WA3: Design creative solutions for <i>complex</i> engineering problems and design systems, components or processes to meet identified needs with appropriate consideration for public health and safety, whole-life cost, net zero carbon as well as resource, cultural, societal, and environmental considerations as required (WK5)</p> <p>Experiential approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical knowledge in real situations <p>Aware of and familiar with late equipment and measurements</p> <p>Digital engineer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to innovate, to develop, to design new and complex products (devices, artefacts, etc.), processes and systems, with specifications incompletely defined and/or competing, that require integration of knowledge from different fields and non-technical – societal, health and safety, environmental, economic and industrial commercial – considerations; • to select and apply the most appropriate and relevant design methodologies or to use creativity to develop new and original design methodologies. • ability to design using knowledge and understanding at the forefront of their engineering specialization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Problem-Solving and Optimization <p>Techniques: Engineers should be adept at using advanced problem-solving and optimization techniques. This includes training in simulation and modeling tools that allow for the efficient design and testing of new products and systems before physical prototypes are developed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary Design Integration: Cultivate the ability to integrate design principles from various engineering disciplines and beyond, incorporating insights from fields such as psychology, ergonomics, and aesthetics. This approach helps in creating products that are not only technically efficient but also user-friendly and marketable.

		<p>and at the state of the art of digital technology.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>• Systems Engineering and Lifecycle Management: Proficiency in systems engineering principles and lifecycle management, including the ability to oversee projects from conception through to disposal, ensuring that all phases of the product lifecycle are sustainable and efficient.</p> <p>• Strategic Use of Digital Twin Technologies: Mastery of digital twin technologies, which create virtual replicas of physical devices to simulate the real world in a safe environment. This capability is vital for testing the impacts of different design scenarios and improving system performance without the risks associated with physical testing.</p> <p>• Circular Economy and Sustainable Design: Integration of circular economy concepts into design practices, focusing on the reusability of products and minimizing waste.</p>
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			<p>Engineers should learn how to design products with an end-of-life strategy that promotes recycling and reuse, aligning with global sustainability targets.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory Expertise and Ethical Design: Deep understanding of regulatory standards and ethical considerations in design, particularly in industries like healthcare and aerospace, where safety and compliance are paramount. This includes keeping abreast of changes in standards and anticipating how new regulations could affect future designs. Entrepreneurial Skills and Market Sensitivity: Development of entrepreneurial skills to bring innovations to market. This involves understanding market demands, competition analysis, and the ability to pitch and sell an engineering concept, aligning technical capabilities with market needs. Collaboration and Communication Skills:
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			<p>Enhanced skills in collaboration and communication, essential for working effectively across multidisciplinary teams and with clients, stakeholders, and other departments. This includes the ability to articulate complex design concepts in clear, persuasive terms and adapt communication styles to different audiences.</p> <p>• Agile Design Practices: Familiarity with agile design methodologies that allow for flexible and iterative design processes, accommodating changes in user requirements, technology, and market dynamics efficiently.</p>
<p>Investigation and Engineering practice</p>	<p>Investigation should not be mixed with research only. Can be achieved with research of course (research-based learning) but also of with innovation -oriented learning.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Business oriented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to use research methods to identify, locate and obtain required data; • ability to conduct searches of literature, • advanced laboratory/workshop skills and ability to design and conduct experimental investigations, critically 	<p>Integration of Emerging Technologies: Develop the ability to integrate and apply emerging technologies such as IoT (Internet of Things), AI (Artificial Intelligence), and blockchain within engineering projects. This includes not only the ability to use these technologies for enhanced data analysis and decision-</p>

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	<p>o Creativity</p> <p>The complexity of modern systems, the consideration of multiple uses and the increasing number of data require the mastery of new methods of data analysis and the consideration of automated mechanisms of adaptation. This must necessarily go beyond the simple ability to program in computer science to systematically use new tools (data analysis, machine learning, artificial intelligence)</p>	<p>evaluate data and draw conclusions;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to investigate in a creative way the application of modern engineering and IT tools to carry out simulation in order to pursue detailed investigations and research of complex technical issues; • Ability to develop critical thinking gather information from the context and analyze and interpret the data 	<p>making but also to foresee their potential impacts and applications in various engineering fields.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis Skills: Enhancement of both quantitative and qualitative analysis skills, enabling engineers to handle and interpret diverse data types from numerical datasets to textual feedback from stakeholders. This dual capability is crucial for comprehensive problem-solving and decision-making. • Interdisciplinary Research Techniques: Cultivation of interdisciplinary research techniques that combine insights and methodologies from multiple fields such as physics, chemistry, biology, and computer science to develop innovative solutions to complex engineering problems. • Ethics in Investigation and Data Handling: Strong
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			<p>emphasis on ethics in investigative practices and data handling, ensuring that all research and development activities are conducted responsibly with a commitment to privacy, confidentiality, and the well-being of society and the environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Management and Resource Optimization: Skills in project management and resource optimization, crucial for conducting effective and efficient investigations. This includes the ability to plan, budget, allocate resources, and manage time effectively in both laboratory and field settings. • Entrepreneurial Research Development: Training in entrepreneurial research development, aiming to transform research outcomes into marketable products or services. This involves understanding the pathways for technology transfer, patenting innovations, and
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			<p>navigating the startup ecosystem.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Engagement and Communication: Enhanced abilities in stakeholder engagement and communication, essential for gathering comprehensive requirements, feedback, and validations. This skill is particularly important when investigations involve community-sensitive or environmentally-impactful projects. Adaptability to Rapid Technological Changes: Preparation for adaptability in the face of rapid technological and methodological changes, ensuring that engineers remain flexible and are able to leverage new tools and approaches as they emerge. Professional Networking and Collaboration: Encouragement of professional networking and collaborative skills,
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			facilitating partnerships that can enhance investigative capabilities and access to cutting-edge research facilities or datasets.
Society and sustainable development	<p>Focus oriented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability, climate change, circular economy • Solidarity Social dimensions <p>Equitable, aimed at “engineering education for all”</p> <p>The ENAEE guideline only has one set of attributes for these competencies that we split to emphasize. For these topics we follow the approach of the Washington accord.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to analyze and evaluate the societal impacts to deliver sustainable solutions for society, the economy and environment. • Ability to design solutions with sustainable methodology. 	<p>Systems Thinking and Holistic Design: Educate engineers to use systems thinking in their approach, enabling them to understand and address complex problems where systems are interconnected and outcomes are interdependent. This involves training in holistic design practices that consider the full lifecycle of products and their long-term impacts on society, economy, and environment.</p> <p>• Sustainable Technologies and Renewable Resources: Develop proficiency in sustainable technologies and the utilization of renewable resources. This includes designing solutions that reduce environmental impact, enhance energy efficiency, and utilize sustainable materials and processes.</p>

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Impact Assessment: Mastery of environmental impact assessment techniques to quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate the environmental consequences of engineering actions before they are carried out. This includes understanding regulatory requirements and best practices in environmental stewardship. • Social Innovation and Community-Centric Design: Encourage social innovation and community-centric design practices that actively involve community stakeholders in the engineering process. This ensures that solutions are not only technically feasible but also socially accepted and beneficial.
<p>Ethics: Understanding and level of practice</p>	<p>2. Humanistic and human literacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guided by ethics - Multi-cultural - Gender sensitive <p>Socio-emotional strong and mindful</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to consult and apply codes of practice and safety regulations ; Respect of Safety and healths and environment protection ; Honesty transparency, respect of intellectual property rules. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Compliance and Ethical Leadership: • Develop a deep understanding of international standards and local codes of practice

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	<p>Ethical leadership: Setting an example and inspiring esteem and respect are among the qualities of an engineer with good leadership.</p>	<p>Respect of societal, gender equality and diversity and environmental considerations as required</p>	<p>across various engineering sectors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train in ethical leadership, emphasizing integrity, accountability, and transparency in all business and engineering practices. • Encourage the ability to navigate and resolve ethical dilemmas in technology and management practices, ensuring decisions contribute positively to the company and community. • Innovative Safety and Risk Management: • Enhance skills in designing and implementing advanced safety measures that go beyond compliance to innovate safer work environments.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate on modern risk assessment technologies and methodologies, including predictive analytics and AI, to proactively manage potential threats to health, safety, and environmental protection. • Intellectual Property (IP) Management: • Equip with knowledge and tools to effectively manage and strategize around intellectual property, including patents, copyrights, and trademarks. • Focus on leveraging IP rights to foster innovation while respecting the legal frameworks and rights of others. • Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in Engineering: • Incorporate training on the impact of diversity, equity, and
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			<p>inclusion on team performance and innovation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop skills for creating inclusive workplaces that attract and retain diverse talent, ensuring that all team members are respected and their contributions valued. • Sustainable Development and Green Engineering: • Strengthen the ability to design and implement solutions that consider long-term environmental impacts, promoting sustainable development. • Train in green engineering principles to minimize waste and pollution, enhancing the environmental friendliness of projects.
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<p>Being a European</p> <p>Understanding the benefits of diversity and interculturality</p>	<p>Mindful of history, geography and political aspects</p> <p>Teamwork in multicultural, multilingual and interdisciplinary environments</p> <p>Involving international experiences</p> <p>Trained to work in international and interdisciplinary projects</p> <p>Democratic challenges are economic, geopolitical and technology (digitalization ...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the European union, its organization, its common values and its main strategic orientation. • Knowledge the challenges Europe is facing and the relation and positioning of Europe within the world. • Ability to use and favor networking opportunities all across Europe industries • Developing a global and inclusive vision with a strong curiosity and pragmatism recognizing the value of other systems and approaches. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deepened Understanding of European Policy and Regulatory Environment: Develop comprehensive knowledge of European policies, trade, labor, environmental, and technological regulations to effectively navigate and leverage these frameworks in business operations. • Multilingual and Multicultural Competence: Encourage proficiency in multiple European languages and enhance cultural competence to facilitate effective communication and negotiation across diverse cultural contexts within Europe.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Use of European Networking and Funding Opportunities: Equip with skills to utilize European networking platforms and professional associations to forge alliances and partnerships, and train in accessing and managing EU funding opportunities for innovation. • Global Business Strategy Development: Develop skills to create business strategies considering Europe's positioning and its trade relations with other world regions, enhancing understanding of Europe's role in
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			<p>global economic systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership in Diverse Settings: Cultivate leadership skills that are adaptive and inclusive, capable of leading diverse teams across the multicultural environments typical in European settings.
<p>Leadership and communication:</p> <p>Role as a team-member and project enabler</p>	<p>Mindsets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global mindset • Cultural agility <p>Valuing learning over knowing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ability to manage complex technical or professional activities or projects that can require new strategic approaches, taking responsibility for decision making. • Ability to communicate with peers but also with the rest of the engineering community and also with a public of non-specialists taking into account cultural, language, and different levels of knowledge. • Ability to lead a project : identify needs, establish requirements, propose 	<p>1. Advanced Project Management Skills:</p> <p>Develop advanced skills in managing and leading complex projects that span multiple disciplines and geographies. This includes training in agile project management methodologies and tools to adapt to changing project scopes and objectives efficiently.</p> <p>2. Strategic Decision-Making and Problem Solving: Enhance the</p>

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		<p>solutions, set goals, share teamwork, follow up an idea from its birth to its realization and adoption by the organization or the company</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpersonal communication 	<p>ability to make strategic decisions under uncertainty, employing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Train in scenario planning and risk management to better anticipate and mitigate potential challenges in project and team management.</p> <p>3. Effective Communication</p> <p>Across Platforms:</p> <p>Equip with skills to effectively communicate across various platforms and mediums, from digital communication tools to public speaking and presentations. Emphasize the importance of clear, persuasive communication tailored to diverse audiences, including technical and non-</p>
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			<p>technical stakeholders.</p> <p>4. Cultural Competence and Global Team Leadership: Focus on developing cultural competence to lead and manage diverse teams effectively in a global context. This includes understanding different cultural dynamics, managing cross-cultural teams, and fostering inclusive work environments.</p> <p>5. Innovative Leadership and Change Management: Train in innovative leadership practices that inspire and drive change within organizations. Develop skills in change management, helping leaders to guide their teams through transitions and ensure that new</p>
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			ideas and solutions are effectively integrated and embraced.
Project Management Finance and intellectual property:	Awareness of Legal Aspects Knowledgeable of innovation processes, patents and proprietary aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and understanding of management and economy principles of a business company, financial concepts and economic decision making, • Knowledge of entrepreneurship (regulation, business models, funding...) • Ability to manage the budget of a project. • Awareness of intellectual property, and patent regulations 	<p>1. Advanced Financial Analysis and Economic Strategy: Develop advanced skills in financial analysis and economic strategy to enhance decision-making capabilities. This includes understanding complex financial metrics, investment appraisal techniques, and the economic implications of engineering decisions on a business's profitability and growth.</p> <p>2. Entrepreneurial Strategy and Business Model Innovation: Enhance knowledge of entrepreneurial strategies and the ability to innovate business models to</p>

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			<p>respond to market changes and technological advancements. Focus on the creation and validation of scalable and sustainable business models that leverage industry trends and customer insights.</p> <p>3. Comprehensive Budget Management and Cost Control: Train in comprehensive project budget management and cost control, including the ability to forecast expenses, manage funding allocations, and optimize resource utilization to meet project objectives without overspending.</p> <p>4. In-depth Intellectual Property Strategy: Deepen understanding of intellectual property</p>
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			<p>management, focusing on how to protect technological innovations, navigate patent laws, and leverage intellectual property rights to gain competitive advantage and generate revenue.</p> <p>5. Risk Management and Compliance:</p> <p>Develop a thorough understanding of risk management practices and compliance requirements, including how to identify, assess, and mitigate financial and legal risks associated with new projects and business ventures.</p>
<p>Lifelong Learning</p>	<p>Attitude and self-aware:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Personalized for joint personal and professional development o Dynamic and continuously evolving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to recognise the need and commitment for and to engage in independent life-long learning; 	<p>Self-Directed Learning Skills:</p> <p>Develop the ability to independently identify learning needs and seek out educational opportunities. This includes fostering skills in self-assessment and reflection to understand</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Modular and flexible: open to the engineer's own discovery o Oriented to lifelong learning o Agility to learn and relearn <p>Ability and agility to change perspectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to undertake further study autonomously. • Adaptability to new and emerging technologies • Commitment to continuous professional 	<p>personal knowledge gaps and the evolving requirements of the industry.</p> <p>Adaptability to Technological Advancements: Cultivate adaptability to keep pace with rapid technological changes. Train in the use of modern learning tools and platforms that support continuous education and skill development, enabling professionals to stay relevant in their fields.</p> <p>Professional Development Planning: Encourage the formulation of personalized professional development plans that align with career goals and industry trends. This includes setting short-term and long-term learning objectives, identifying relevant courses, workshops, and seminars, and evaluating progress regularly.</p> <p>Networking and Collaborative Learning: Promote the development of a professional network to</p>
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			<p>facilitate collaborative learning and knowledge exchange. This involves engaging with professional associations, attending industry conferences, and participating in forums and discussion groups relevant to their fields.</p> <p>Critical Evaluation of Emerging Trends: Enhance the ability to critically evaluate emerging trends and technologies to determine their relevance and potential impact on one’s career and industry. This includes training in critical thinking and analysis skills to discern between fads and fundamental shifts.</p>
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3.2 Summary of Learning Outcomes for a Successful Entrepreneurial and Industrial Career

The collaboration between EELISA partner universities is crucial in preparing students for successful careers in entrepreneurship and SME management. These institutions offer a comprehensive curriculum that provides deep insights into the entrepreneurship ecosystem, emphasizing the importance of SMEs in economic growth and innovation.

Students engage in a multidisciplinary learning environment, gaining skills in business creation, strategic management, and problem-solving. They learn to critically analyze business dynamics, develop comprehensive business plans, and navigate financial and legal frameworks. This cooperative educational framework leverages the collective resources of partner universities, enhancing learning experiences and preparing graduates to innovate and lead in the global economy. The summary of the learning outcomes is listed below:

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- Gain a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurship, encompassing its core concepts and principles.
- Identify and categorize various methods for establishing new ventures.
- Articulate the broader economic advantages associated with entrepreneurship.
- Establish connections between entrepreneurship and its impact on the economy.
- Grasp fundamental concepts related to intrapreneurship and its significance.
- Recognize the importance of generating business ideas and implementing entrepreneurship policies.
- Assess the pivotal role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in driving economic growth.
- Define and outline the characteristics of SMEs within the economic landscape.
- Illustrate the processes involved in the establishment and operation of SMEs.
- Analyze the interrelations among different operational processes within SMEs.
- Apply conceptual knowledge to analyze the dynamics of new business creation and expansion.
- Demonstrate an understanding of creativity and its relevance in entrepreneurial endeavors.
- Define and discuss the concept of innovation within the context of entrepreneurship.
- Evaluate the financial requirements during the startup phase of a business venture.
- Interpret the legal status and regulatory framework applicable to entrepreneurial ventures.
- Comprehend the fundamentals of business planning and its advantages in guiding entrepreneurial activities.
- Identify the key components and sections of a comprehensive business plan.
- Assess the future prospects and potential success of entrepreneurial ventures.
- Formulate strategic suggestions to enhance the future success and sustainability of businesses.
- Demonstrate proficiency in personal management skills and problem-solving strategies.
- Effectively report on the challenges and propose solutions pertinent to small enterprises.
- Analyze management, production, marketing, financial, and public administration issues encountered by small enterprises.
- Develop strategies and formulas to address the multifaceted challenges faced by small enterprises

3.3 Studying Expectations from Educational Programs

Studying at a university within the EELISA alliance offers unique advantages tailored to propel students towards successful industrial and entrepreneurial careers. With a focus on providing a holistic education, EELISA member institutions deliver a curriculum designed to equip students with not only foundational knowledge in their chosen disciplines but also practical insights into industry dynamics and entrepreneurial principles. By immersing students in a rich ecosystem of collaborative

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initiatives and exchange programs facilitated by EELISA, universities within the alliance offer unparalleled opportunities for hands-on learning and real-world experience. Moreover, the international network of EELISA institutions exposes students to diverse industrial contexts, fostering cross-cultural understanding and global perspectives essential for thriving in today's interconnected world. Through a combination of rigorous academic training and practical skill development, studying at a university of the EELISA alliance positions students at the forefront of innovation and prepares them to excel as leaders in their chosen fields upon graduation.

Industry Immersion and Practical Experience:

- Structured internships, co-op programs, or industry-sponsored projects to provide hands-on experience in real-world engineering environments.
- Exposure to industry practices, processes, and standards through site visits, guest lectures by industry professionals, and collaborative projects with industry partners.
- Opportunities for students to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, solving industry-relevant problems and gaining insights into the application of engineering principles in the field.

Business and Entrepreneurship Education:

- Integration of business and entrepreneurship courses into the engineering curriculum to equip students with essential knowledge and skills for commercializing their innovations.
- Instruction on market analysis, product development, pricing strategies, and business model canvas to help students understand the commercial viability of their engineering solutions.
- Entrepreneurship-focused workshops, seminars, and mentorship programs to nurture students' entrepreneurial mindset and provide guidance on launching and managing startup ventures.

Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property (IP) Management:

- Education on technology transfer processes, including patenting, licensing, and technology commercialization, to help students protect and monetize their intellectual property.
- Training on IP management principles and best practices, emphasizing the importance of safeguarding innovations and maximizing their value in industry partnerships and collaborations.
- Collaboration with technology transfer offices and legal experts to provide students with practical guidance on navigating IP issues and negotiating licensing agreements.

Market Research and Product Development:

- Instruction on conducting market research, identifying customer needs, and assessing market demand to inform product development decisions.
- Hands-on experience in designing, prototyping, and testing engineering solutions with a focus on meeting market requirements and addressing customer pain points.
- Exposure to lean startup methodologies and agile product development practices to enable iterative refinement and rapid adaptation to market feedback.

Professional Skills Development:

- Training in communication, negotiation, and presentation skills to effectively communicate engineering concepts, ideas, and proposals to industry stakeholders.

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- Workshops on project management, teamwork, and leadership to prepare students for collaborative work environments and leadership roles in industry settings.
- Opportunities for networking, mentorship, and career development to help students build professional relationships, explore career pathways, and access job opportunities in the industry.

Ethics and Social Responsibility:

- Integration of ethics education into the engineering curriculum, emphasizing ethical decision-making, social responsibility, and sustainability considerations in engineering practice.
- Discussion of case studies and ethical dilemmas relevant to engineering ethics, encouraging critical reflection and ethical reasoning skills.
- Incorporation of sustainability principles into engineering design and innovation processes, promoting environmentally conscious and socially responsible engineering solutions.

By incorporating these elements into educational programs in engineering, institutions can better prepare students for successful industrial and entrepreneurial careers by equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and mindset to thrive in the competitive and dynamic landscape of the engineering industry.

3.3.1 Classical Industrial Skills

Classical industrial skills are fundamental competencies that underpin various engineering disciplines, encompassing a broad spectrum of abilities essential for successful industrial operations across sectors. These skills entail a deep understanding of manufacturing processes, materials, and techniques, which are applicable to fields ranging from mechanical and electrical engineering to civil and chemical engineering. Mastery of classical industrial skills involves proficiency in problem-solving, critical thinking, and attention to detail, enabling engineers to optimize processes, enhance productivity, and ensure the quality of outputs. Moreover, classical industrial skills encompass effective communication, collaboration, and project management abilities, facilitating teamwork and coordination within multidisciplinary teams. In today's rapidly evolving industrial landscape, these foundational skills remain invaluable, serving as the cornerstone of innovation and progress across diverse engineering domains. Cooperation among technical universities within alliances like EELISA offers students a wealth of opportunities to enhance their industrial skills:

- **Exchange Programs:** Participation in exchange programs allows students to study at partner universities, exposing them to different industrial practices, technologies, and methodologies. This cross-cultural experience broadens their perspective and fosters adaptability, essential skills for success in diverse industrial environments.
- **Joint Research Projects:** Collaborative research projects between universities and industry partners provide students with hands-on experience in solving real-world problems. Working alongside professionals and academics, students can apply theoretical knowledge to practical challenges, developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.
- **Internships and Co-op Programs:** Alliances often facilitate internships and cooperative education programs with industry partners. These opportunities enable students to gain valuable work experience, develop technical skills, and build professional networks, enhancing their employability and readiness for the industrial workforce.
- **Industry-Driven Curriculum:** Universities can collaborate with industry partners to develop curriculum content that aligns with current industry needs and trends. This ensures that students graduate with relevant skills and knowledge that are directly applicable to industrial settings, increasing their competitiveness in the job market.

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- Workshops and Seminars: Joint workshops, seminars, and industry symposiums organized by alliance universities provide students with exposure to cutting-edge technologies, industry best practices, and emerging trends. These events offer opportunities for skill development, networking, and knowledge exchange with industry professionals.
- Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programs: Universities can collaborate to offer entrepreneurship and innovation programs that equip students with the skills and mindset to launch their own ventures or drive innovation within existing organizations. Access to mentorship, funding opportunities, and incubation facilities within the alliance enhances students' entrepreneurial capabilities.
- Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration: Alliances encourage collaboration across different engineering disciplines, allowing students to work on interdisciplinary projects that mirror real-world industrial challenges. This interdisciplinary approach fosters creativity, innovation, and the ability to tackle complex problems from multiple perspectives.

3.3.2 Classical Entrepreneurial Skills

Cooperation among technical universities within EELISA creates numerous opportunities for students to develop and enhance their entrepreneurial skills:

- Entrepreneurship Programs and Courses: Collaborative efforts among universities can lead to the development of specialized entrepreneurship programs and courses. These programs provide students with theoretical knowledge and practical skills related to business planning, market analysis, financial management, and venture creation.
- Incubation Centers and Start-up Support: Jointly established incubation centers and start-up support initiatives within the alliance offer students access to resources, mentorship, and funding opportunities to nurture their entrepreneurial ideas and launch start-up ventures.
- Cross-disciplinary Collaboration: Alliances encourage cross-disciplinary collaboration, enabling students from different engineering disciplines to work together on entrepreneurial projects. This collaboration fosters creativity, diversity of thought, and innovation, essential ingredients for entrepreneurial success.
- Industry Partnerships and Networking Events: Cooperative efforts with industry partners and networking events organized by the alliance provide students with opportunities to connect with entrepreneurs, investors, and industry professionals. These interactions facilitate mentorship, knowledge exchange, and potential partnerships for entrepreneurial ventures.
- Hackathons and Innovation Challenges: Collaborative hackathons, innovation challenges, and entrepreneurship competitions organized by the alliance offer students platforms to showcase their entrepreneurial ideas, receive feedback from experts, and win prizes or funding to further develop their ventures.
- Access to Funding and Resources: Alliance partnerships may grant students access to funding sources, grants, and research funding earmarked for entrepreneurial initiatives. Additionally, students may benefit from access to shared facilities, equipment, and research infrastructure to support their entrepreneurial endeavors.
- International Exposure and Market Access: Collaboration with universities and industry partners across borders provides students with international exposure and access to global markets. This exposure allows students to gain insights into diverse cultural and market dynamics, facilitating the development of globally scalable entrepreneurial ventures.
- Mentorship and Guidance: Alliances can facilitate mentorship programs, connecting students with experienced entrepreneurs, industry leaders, and alumni who can provide guidance, advice, and support throughout their entrepreneurial journey.

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3.3.3 Further, non-classical skills

Non-classical soft skills encompass a diverse set of interpersonal, communication, leadership, and adaptability skills that go beyond traditional technical competencies. These skills include attributes such as emotional intelligence, teamwork, adaptability, communication, leadership, creativity, problem-solving, and cultural awareness.

- **Cross-Cultural Collaboration:** Collaborative projects and exchange programs within the alliance expose students to diverse cultural backgrounds and working styles. This fosters cross-cultural communication, empathy, and teamwork, enhancing their ability to collaborate effectively in multicultural environments.
- **Leadership Opportunities:** Alliance partnerships provide students with opportunities to take on leadership roles in collaborative projects, student organizations, and extracurricular activities. Leading teams and initiatives develops their leadership, decision-making, and conflict resolution skills.
- **Communication and Presentation Skills:** Cooperative projects, seminars, and workshops organized by the alliance offer platforms for students to practice and improve their communication and presentation skills. Presenting research findings, pitching ideas, and engaging in discussions with peers and professionals enhance their ability to articulate ideas clearly and persuasively.
- **Networking and Relationship Building:** Collaboration with students, faculty, and industry professionals from different universities within the alliance facilitates networking and relationship building. Engaging in collaborative activities and attending alliance events provides opportunities for students to expand their professional network and build valuable relationships.
- **Adaptability and Flexibility:** Engaging in cross-disciplinary projects and international collaborations requires students to be adaptable and flexible in their approach. Adapting to different work environments, methodologies, and cultural norms enhances their resilience and ability to thrive in dynamic and uncertain situations.
- **Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking:** Collaborative projects and research initiatives challenge students to think critically and creatively to solve complex problems. Working on interdisciplinary teams and tackling real-world challenges develops their problem-solving skills and encourages innovative thinking.
- **Time Management and Organization:** Balancing academic coursework, collaborative projects, and extracurricular activities within the alliance requires effective time management and organization skills. Juggling multiple responsibilities enhances students' ability to prioritize tasks, meet deadlines, and manage their time efficiently.
- **Emotional Intelligence and Empathy:** Interacting with diverse individuals and navigating team dynamics within collaborative projects cultivates emotional intelligence and empathy. Understanding and empathizing with the perspectives and experiences of others fosters effective communication, conflict resolution, and relationship building skills.

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3.4 Improvement of Learning Outcomes for a Successful Industrial and Entrepreneurial Career within the EELISA Alliance

3.4.1 Courses

The EELISA alliance offers a diverse range of courses designed to prepare students for successful industrial and entrepreneurial careers, with options tailored to local, hybrid, and international formats that emphasize mobility:

- **Local Presence Courses:**
 Local presence courses are offered at individual member universities, providing students with access to foundational knowledge and specialized skills relevant to their respective disciplines and local industries.
 These courses are taught by faculty members with expertise in specific domains and often incorporate practical, hands-on learning experiences, such as laboratory sessions, workshops, and industry visits.
 Examples of local presence courses include core engineering modules, business fundamentals, and specialized electives that align with local industry needs and academic strengths.
- **Hybrid Form Courses:**
 Hybrid form courses blend traditional classroom instruction with online learning components, offering students flexibility and accessibility while maintaining academic rigor.
 These courses leverage digital platforms and educational technologies to deliver lectures, assignments, and interactive learning activities, allowing students to engage with course materials at their own pace and convenience.
 Hybrid form courses may incorporate virtual labs, simulations, and collaborative projects that enable students to apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios, fostering practical skills development.
 This format allows for increased scalability and reach, enabling students from different universities within the alliance to participate and collaborate effectively.
- **International Presence with Mobility:**
 Courses with an international presence and mobility component provide students with the opportunity to study and collaborate across borders, gaining exposure to diverse cultural, industrial, and entrepreneurial environments.
 These courses may involve joint modules offered collaboratively by multiple EELISA member universities, allowing students to access specialized expertise and resources beyond their home institution.
 Mobility programs within the alliance facilitate student exchanges, study abroad opportunities, and international internships, enabling students to immerse themselves in different cultural contexts and gain first-hand experience in global industries and markets.
 Students participating in international courses with mobility components develop cross-cultural communication, adaptability, and global perspective, essential skills for success in today's interconnected world.

Industrial PhD programs represent a crucial bridge between academic research and industry application, offering profound benefits for both doctoral candidates and the business sector. These programs are designed to foster a deep integration of academic research insights with real-world industrial challenges, creating a symbiotic relationship that enhances innovation and practical problem-solving skills in emerging professionals.

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Industrial PhD programs provide candidates with the opportunity to work directly with companies while pursuing their doctoral studies, thus ensuring that their research is not only theoretically robust but also immediately applicable to industrial needs. This direct application encourages a flow of knowledge and technology between universities and industries, driving forward innovations that are both scientifically advanced and commercially viable.

Recognizing the significance of these programs, a symposium session on the best practices of partner institutions was organized during the 2023 Istanbul meeting. This session highlighted the successes and varied approaches of several partner universities that already have thriving industrial PhD programs. The discussions and exchanges during this symposium provided valuable insights into effective strategies for integrating doctoral research with industrial application, which are essential for nurturing the next generation of industry leaders.

The positive feedback and outcomes reported by institutions with active industrial PhD programs have inspired other partner universities to consider initiating similar programs. The enthusiasm and interest generated by the symposium have paved the way for a broader implementation of these programs across the EELISA consortium. This expansion is seen not only as a step towards enhancing the practical impact of academic research but also as a strategic move to strengthen the ties between academia and industry across Europe.

To further this initiative, implementing industrial PhD programs at the EELISA level could be an integral task for upcoming chapters of the EELISA project. Establishing a standardized yet flexible framework for these programs across the consortium could help streamline processes, share best practices, and foster a cooperative environment that benefits all stakeholders. This framework would not only support the creation of new industrial PhD opportunities but also enhance the quality and relevance of existing programs.

Overall, the EELISA alliance offers a comprehensive portfolio of courses that cater to the diverse needs and aspirations of students preparing for industrial and entrepreneurial careers. Whether through local presence, hybrid form, or international presence with mobility, these courses provide students with the knowledge, skills, and experiences necessary to excel in dynamic and competitive professional landscapes.

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4 EELISA Level Collaboration in Technology Transfer

4.1 Integrating Learning Outcomes with Technology Transfer Practices

The connection between the first part of the deliverable, focused on refining Learning Outcomes, and the second part, emphasizing Technology Transfer Practices, represents a strategic alignment of educational objectives with practical, industry-oriented execution. This integration is vital for equipping students with the skills necessary to not only innovate but also effectively transition those innovations into market-ready technologies and products.

The surveys conducted among the EELISA consortium members have been instrumental in this process, providing valuable data that reflects the current state of technology transfer activities and the needs within each institution. The insights gained from these surveys inform the continuous enhancement of the learning outcomes by identifying specific skills gaps and opportunities for improvement in the curriculum. For instance, if a recurring theme in the survey feedback highlights a lack of expertise in intellectual property management among students, the curriculum can be adjusted to include more in-depth courses on this subject.

Furthermore, the conclusions drawn from the survey data directly feed into the development of targeted recommendations for enhancing educational programs. These recommendations ensure that the programs are not only theoretically robust but also practically relevant, providing students with the competencies needed to navigate the complexities of technology transfer effectively. For example, based on the survey results indicating the need for greater practical experience in real-world settings, the learning outcomes could be adjusted to incorporate more experiential learning opportunities such as internships in industry or participatory projects in university-led tech transfer initiatives.

By aligning the learning outcomes with the insights gained from technology transfer practices, EELISA is able to create a feedback loop where educational content is continually refined based on practical outcomes and industry requirements. This approach ensures that the consortium remains at the cutting edge of engineering education and entrepreneurship, fully preparing students to meet the demands of the global market and to contribute innovatively to their respective fields. This strategic alignment underscores the project's commitment to producing not only skilled engineers but also capable innovators who are ready to make significant impacts in technology and society.

On 10 April 2024 a Technology Transfer workshop was held with the participation of the partner institutes delegates from their technology transfer offices. The main topics were best practices of their technology transfer processes, as well as EELISA level contribution ideas. The event was organised by BME, WP6.

Furthermore, a survey was carried out among consortium members to map their technology transfer practices and their challenges they face. In the following chapter the survey is evaluated.

Methodology of Information Integration into the Deliverable

The methodology to inform the EELISA InnoCORE project's deliverable involved a targeted survey (see Annex) and a focused workshop, which collectively enriched the development of pertinent learning outcomes for industrial and entrepreneurial careers:

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Survey on Technology Transfer Practices:

- Objective: The survey aimed to capture detailed insights on current technology transfer practices across partner institutions.
- Execution: Distributed to partners' TTO offices involved in technology transfer at each partner university, the survey gathered data on existing frameworks, challenges, and opportunities in IP management and technology transfer.
- Impact: The responses provided a comprehensive overview of the institutional capabilities and gaps, informing the need for specific skills in the educational programs.

Technology Transfer Workshop:

- Date: Held on 10 April 2024, this workshop aimed to deepen the understanding from the survey and foster collaborative problem-solving.
- Activities: Participants discussed survey findings, shared experiences, and developed collective strategies to tackle common challenges identified in the technology transfer domain.
- Outcome: The workshop facilitated real-time knowledge exchange and consensus-building on effective practices and educational enhancements.

Integration into Learning Outcomes:

Synthesis and Application: Insights from both the survey and the workshop were synthesized to directly inform and refine the learning outcomes. This ensured the educational recommendations were robust, addressing identified needs in technology transfer and IP management.

Development of Learning Outcomes: The data helped tailor learning outcomes that equip students with critical skills in IP rights, commercialization, and strategic technology management, crucial for fostering a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career.

In conclusion, the combined methodology of a focused survey and workshop provided a dynamic foundation for developing targeted learning outcomes. This approach ensured that the educational programs are directly aligned with the evolving needs of the industry and prepared students effectively for the challenges of technology transfer in their future careers

4.2 Evaluation of the Surveys on Technology Transfer Practices of Partner Institutes

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4.1.1. Greatest Challenges

7. What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?

8 válasz

TTOs play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between academic research and real-world applications, yet they face a myriad of challenges that hinder their effectiveness. According to responses from the participant universities, several key challenges stand out prominently.

Administrative burden emerges as a significant obstacle, with half of the respondents acknowledging its impact. This burden encompasses bureaucratic processes, regulatory compliance requirements, and extensive documentation needs, diverting resources away from core activities like technology transfer and commercialization. Streamlining administrative processes and adopting efficient workflows could alleviate this burden and enhance TTO efficiency.

Lack of resources poses another formidable challenge, as identified by the majority of respondents. Insufficient funding and staffing levels limit TTOs' ability to effectively identify, protect, and commercialize intellectual property. Moreover, inadequate resources hinder TTOs from providing necessary support for innovation and technology transfer initiatives. Increasing investment in TTOs, both in terms of financial resources and personnel, is essential to address this challenge and unlock their full potential.

Researcher attitudes that prioritize publication over commercialization represent a cultural barrier within academic institutions. While publications are valued for academic advancement, fostering a mindset that recognizes the importance of commercialization alongside scholarly achievements is crucial. TTOs must collaborate with researchers to cultivate an entrepreneurial culture that encourages the translation of research into tangible societal impact.

Similarly, **the lack of entrepreneurial skills** within TTO teams or among colleagues poses a significant impediment to technology transfer efforts. Enhancing the entrepreneurial capacity of TTO staff and researchers through training programs and mentorship initiatives can empower them to identify market opportunities, negotiate licensing agreements, and support startup ventures more effectively.

Lack of market connections and **the dominance of large companies** in business negotiations further compound the challenges faced by TTOs. Establishing and nurturing robust networks with industry stakeholders, facilitating partnerships, and providing tailored support for startups can help

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TTOs overcome these barriers and facilitate successful technology transfer and commercialization endeavors.

In addressing these challenges, collaborative efforts between universities, industry partners, and policymakers are crucial. By investing in resources, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, and facilitating connections between academia and industry, TTOs can navigate these obstacles and fulfill their mandate of translating research into real-world impact effectively.

8. Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?

8 válasz

The responses from seven universities regarding the provision of self-awareness development and communication training facilitated by psychologists to support career building underscore the varying approaches and recognition of its importance in nurturing students' professional growth. Encouragingly, 50% of the universities already offer such training, signaling a proactive stance towards equipping students with essential skills for navigating their career paths, especially in the dynamic landscape of startups and innovation. However, it's noteworthy that 25% of the universities indicated they do not provide this training, while another 25% acknowledged the need for it but have yet to implement such programs. These findings highlight both progress and opportunities for further investment in supporting students' career development through self-awareness and communication training.

In the context of startups and innovation, self-awareness development and effective communication skills are invaluable assets for aspiring entrepreneurs and innovators. Startup environments often demand individuals to navigate ambiguity, handle setbacks, and communicate their ideas persuasively to stakeholders. By providing training facilitated by psychologists, universities can help students cultivate self-awareness, resilience, and emotional intelligence – qualities essential for success in the fast-paced and high-pressure world of startups. Moreover, effective communication skills are paramount for building strong teams, securing funding, attracting customers, and forging strategic partnerships, all of which are critical aspects of launching and scaling innovative ventures.

Investing in self-awareness development and communication training aligns with the broader goals of fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and culture within universities. By equipping students with these foundational skills, universities not only enhance their employability but also empower them to become resilient, adaptable, and empathetic leaders in the startup ecosystem. Moreover, by leveraging the expertise of psychologists, universities can provide tailored support to address the unique challenges and stressors that students may encounter on their entrepreneurial journeys, ultimately enhancing their ability to navigate uncertainty and thrive in the face of adversity.

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9. Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?

8 válasz

The feedback from seven universities on offering non-violent/assertive communication training to students reveals a varied landscape of approaches and perspectives, which could significantly impact students' innovation, their roles in startups, and ultimately their success. Encouragingly, the fact that 37.5% of the universities already offer such training indicates a recognition of its importance in fostering healthy communication skills among students, a crucial aspect for their involvement in startups and innovative ventures.

However, the finding that an equal percentage (37.5%) of universities have not yet integrated this training into their curriculum or extracurricular activities suggests a potential gap in preparing students for the challenges they may encounter in entrepreneurial endeavors. Effective communication skills are paramount for students engaged in startups, as they navigate team dynamics, pitch ideas, negotiate partnerships, and communicate with stakeholders.

Moreover, the response indicating that 25% of the universities acknowledge the need for such training but haven't implemented it underscores the awareness among educational institutions about the importance of communication skills in fostering innovation and entrepreneurial success. Addressing this gap is essential, as effective communication can determine the success or failure of a startup, influencing everything from team cohesion and productivity to investor relations and customer engagement.

These findings emphasize the critical role of non-violent/assertive communication training in equipping students with the skills they need to thrive in the startup ecosystem. By enhancing their ability to communicate effectively, universities can empower students to collaborate more productively, resolve conflicts constructively, and articulate their ideas persuasively – all of which are essential for success in entrepreneurial ventures.

Moving forward, universities should prioritize the integration of communication skills development into their entrepreneurship programs, ensuring that students are adequately prepared to navigate the challenges and opportunities of startup ventures. Collaboration among universities, sharing best practices, and leveraging external resources can further enhance the impact of communication training initiatives, ultimately fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurial excellence among students.

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a. TTO Support Teams

11. Is there a specialist on campus who works with the TTO to support teams with team building and mediation?

8 válasz

From the responses, it appears that a significant portion of the universities surveyed have a professional dedicated to supporting startup and spinoff teams with team-building and mediation. Specifically, 37.5% of the universities answered affirmatively to having such a professional in place. This suggests that there is recognition among these universities of the importance of team-building and mediation in the context of startups and spinoffs.

However, it's noteworthy that another 37.5% of the universities indicated that they do not have such a professional, indicating potential gaps in support for startup and spinoff teams in those institutions. This finding underscores the need for universities to consider the benefits of having dedicated professionals who can provide expertise in team-building and mediation, thereby facilitating the success and effectiveness of startup initiatives.

Additionally, the 25% of universities that responded "no, but there is a need for" indicate a recognition of the importance of this role, suggesting that there may be plans or aspirations to address this need in the future. This response highlights a potential area for growth and development within university support structures for startups and spinoffs, indicating a willingness to adapt and improve to better serve the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Skill Set for Startup and Spinoff Supporters

Ideal startup and spinoff supporters within a university's ecosystem should possess a blend of skills, experience, and qualities that enable them to effectively nurture and guide entrepreneurial ventures. The ideal startup and spinoff supporters should:

- have a diverse skill set encompassing areas such as business development, marketing, finance, legal knowledge, and technology transfer. This enables them to provide comprehensive support across various aspects of startup and spinoff development.
- have experience in entrepreneurship or startup creation themselves can provide valuable insights and empathy for the challenges faced by founders. This firsthand experience can inform their guidance and mentorship.
- have strong interpersonal skills for fostering collaboration and resolving conflicts within startup teams. Ideal supporters should be adept at team-building and mediation, creating cohesive and productive environments.

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- be well-versed in funding opportunities available to startups and spinoffs, including grants, venture capital, and angel investment. This knowledge allows them to advise teams on fundraising strategies and connect them with relevant funding sources.
- have a robust network within the entrepreneurial ecosystem, invaluable for opening doors to resources, mentorship, partnerships, and potential customers or investors. Ideal supporters should have extensive connections that they can leverage for the benefit of startup and spinoff teams.
- demonstrate success in supporting startups and spinoffs, evidenced by the growth and accomplishments of ventures they have worked with, adds credibility and trustworthiness to their guidance.
- be committed to continuous learning and staying updated on industry trends, best practices, and emerging technologies.
- be passionate about fostering innovation and entrepreneurship within the university community. Their dedication to the success of startup ventures should be evident in their actions and commitment to going above and beyond to support founders.

By embodying these qualities and capabilities, ideal startup and spinoff supporters can significantly enhance the growth and success of entrepreneurial ventures emerging from universities.

Number of staff

Determining the ideal number of staff for supporting startups and spinoffs within a university's technology transfer office (TTO) depends on various factors:

- - including the size of the university,
- BME: around 20.000 students
- - the volume of entrepreneurial activity, and
- BME:
- - the level of support required by startup teams.

BME:

Number of the staff for supporting startups and spinoffs

BME: 4 person (2 lawyer, 2 business developer)

Recommendations for building the support services for startups and spinoffs

Begin by assessing the demand for startup and spinoff support services within the university. This can be done through surveys, consultations with faculty and students, and analysis of past entrepreneurial initiatives. Understanding the level of demand will provide insights into the staffing needs.

Design the staffing structure to be scalable to accommodate fluctuations in demand over time. Startup ecosystems can experience periods of rapid growth or lulls, so having a flexible staffing approach allows the TTO to adjust accordingly.

Aim to assemble a multi-disciplinary team with expertise in various areas relevant to startups, including business development, technology transfer, intellectual property, marketing, finance, and legal affairs. Having a diverse team enables comprehensive support for startup ventures.

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Consider the optimal staff-to-startup team ratio based on the level of support required by each venture. While there is no one-size-fits-all ratio, a general guideline could be to assign staff members to a manageable number of startup teams to ensure personalized attention and effective support.

Strive to maximize the efficiency and productivity of the staff by leveraging technology, streamlining processes, and implementing best practices in startup support. This allows the TTO to serve a larger number of startup teams with existing resources.

Foster collaboration and synergy among staff members to capitalize on their collective expertise and strengths. Encourage knowledge sharing, cross-training, and teamwork to enhance the overall effectiveness of the TTO's support services.

Continuously evaluate the performance and impact of the TTO's support services to inform staffing decisions. Solicit feedback from startup teams, faculty, and external stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and optimization.

Ultimately, the ideal number of staff for a TTO supporting startups and spinoffs will vary depending on the specific context and needs of the university's entrepreneurial ecosystem. Regular assessment, flexibility, and a focus on delivering high-quality support are key to optimizing staffing levels and maximizing the TTO's impact on startup success.

12. Is there a dedicated staff (e.g. administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) to support researchers in practice in turning inventions into products?

8 válasz

The majority of universities (62.5%) report having dedicated staff to support researchers in IP commercialization. This suggests that these institutions have recognized the importance of providing professional assistance, including legal, financial, and project management support, which are crucial for transforming inventions into viable products.

However, the responses also highlight significant gaps in support. The combined 37.5% (12.5% noting a need and 25% indicating absence) reveal that a considerable number of universities either lack the necessary support staff or recognize an unmet need for such resources. The fact that some universities identify a need for dedicated staff suggests that while the importance of this support is acknowledged, there may be resource constraints or institutional barriers preventing the implementation of these roles.

The survey explored the willingness of universities to collaborate at a European level through the development of start-up teams based on university research results. This collaboration can significantly enhance innovation and commercialization of academic research across Europe.

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The survey examined two main aspects of this collaboration:

Willingness to Welcome Foreign Startups for Teamwork:

4. Would your university welcome a foreign startup (who is also a university student) for teamwork?

7 válasz

All respondents (7 universities) indicated a positive willingness to welcome a foreign startup who is also a university student for teamwork. This unanimous agreement highlights a strong openness among universities to engage in international collaboration, which can foster cross-border innovation and the sharing of diverse perspectives.

Preferences Regarding Team Composition:

5. What would be your preferences?

6 válasz

Idea Guy/Girl" Without a Team: 4 universities expressed a preference for collaborating with an individual who has a promising idea but lacks a team. This indicates a readiness to support and nurture innovative ideas from their inception stage, providing resources and guidance to develop these concepts into viable projects.

"Member Looking for a Project": 5 universities preferred to collaborate with individuals who are looking to join an existing project. This preference suggests that many universities value the addition

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of skilled and motivated team members who can contribute to and enhance ongoing projects, thereby accelerating their progress and potential for commercialization.

The survey results reveal a strong willingness among universities to engage in collaborative efforts at the European level. The unanimous positive response to welcoming foreign startupper underscores the potential for creating a vibrant, interconnected ecosystem where ideas and talent can move freely across borders. This openness can lead to the cross-pollination of ideas and the development of robust, diverse start-up teams.

The mixed preferences regarding team composition reflect the different strategic approaches universities take towards innovation. Some institutions focus on nurturing nascent ideas by providing comprehensive support to idea generators, while others emphasize strengthening existing projects by integrating new, capable members.

The willingness of universities to collaborate with foreign startupper and their varied preferences in team composition highlight a promising landscape for European-level collaboration in start-up development. By leveraging these collaborative opportunities, universities can enhance the commercialization of research results, drive innovation, and contribute to the growth of a dynamic, integrated European research and innovation ecosystem. To maximize these benefits, universities should continue to foster an environment that supports both the incubation of new ideas and the enrichment of ongoing projects through the inclusion of diverse, international talent.

7. Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

6 válasz

The unanimous positive response indicates a strong enthusiasm and commitment among universities to foster entrepreneurship and innovation through structured, immersive programs like startup summer camps. These camps offer a unique opportunity for university students and researchers to develop their ideas, gain practical experience, and collaborate with peers and mentors in a supportive environment.

Potential Benefits of Startup Summer Camps include:

- **Skill Development** - Participants can gain essential entrepreneurial skills, including business planning, marketing, financial management, and pitch preparation.
- **Networking Opportunities** - The camps facilitate connections between students, researchers, industry experts, and potential investors, fostering valuable relationships that can support future ventures.

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- Cross-Cultural Collaboration - Hosting these camps in cooperation with various universities encourages cross-cultural exchange, enriching the participants' perspectives and enhancing the diversity of ideas.
- Accelerated Innovation -The focused, intensive nature of the camps can accelerate the development and refinement of startup ideas, leading to more viable and market-ready projects.
- Increased Visibility - Universities hosting or participating in these camps can enhance their reputation as leaders in innovation and entrepreneurship, attracting more talent and resources to their programs.

The strong support for startup summer camps among universities reflects a collective recognition of their value in promoting entrepreneurial skills, fostering collaboration, and accelerating innovation. By hosting these camps, universities can create a dynamic environment that nurtures the growth of new ventures and contributes to the broader ecosystem of research commercialization and startup development. This enthusiastic backing also underscores the potential for fruitful cooperation at a European level, leveraging the strengths and resources of multiple institutions to drive significant advancements in entrepreneurship education and practice.

2. How Can EELISA Improve on TTOs of Member Universities?

Funding and Grants: Developing and supporting TTOs is a long-term investment that many universities do not have the resources to plan for because the government does not provide them, and the revenues from the involvement of industrial partners in innovation are used mainly for overheads and salaries. Consequently, there is limited potential for investment and growth in TTOs under current funding models.

To address this challenge, EELISA could establish dedicated funding mechanisms tailored to support TTOs' activities. By providing financial resources specifically earmarked for technology transfer initiatives, EELISA can empower TTOs to expand their operations, enhance their capabilities, and foster a more conducive environment for innovation and entrepreneurship. Additionally, EELISA could offer grants and funding opportunities designed to incentivize collaboration between TTOs, researchers, and industry partners, facilitating the translation of research outcomes into tangible societal impact.

Furthermore, EELISA could advocate for policy changes at the national and European levels to secure sustainable funding streams for TTOs. By highlighting the importance of technology transfer in driving economic growth, job creation, and innovation, EELISA can garner support for increased public investment in TTOs. This could involve lobbying policymakers to allocate a portion of research and innovation funding specifically for technology transfer activities, ensuring that TTOs have the necessary resources to fulfill their mission effectively. Overall, by prioritizing funding and grants targeted at TTOs, EELISA can play a pivotal role in strengthening Europe's innovation ecosystem and maximizing the impact of academic research on society.

Capacity Building: EELISA can facilitate capacity building initiatives for TTO staff, providing them with training and professional development opportunities in areas such as intellectual property management, technology commercialisation (sales potential), negotiation and entrepreneurship skills development, market research, in-house product development, people management, etc.

Networking and Collaboration: EELISA can foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among TTOs across European universities. This could involve organizing workshops, conferences, and networking events where TTO professionals can share best practices, learn from each other's experiences, and form partnerships for joint initiatives.

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Access to Expertise and Resources: EELISA can establish mechanisms for TTOs to access specialized expertise and resources, such as legal and business advisory services, market research, and investor networks. This could involve creating centralized platforms or databases where TTOs can connect with relevant experts and resources.

Promotion of Innovation Ecosystems: EELISA can support the development of vibrant innovation ecosystems within European universities by incentivizing collaboration between TTOs, research centers, industry partners, and startup incubators. This could involve funding initiatives that promote university-industry collaboration, technology transfer, and the commercialization of research outcomes.

Policy Advocacy and Support: EELISA can advocate for policies and regulations that facilitate technology transfer and innovation within the European Union. This could include advocating for streamlined intellectual property laws, funding mechanisms for technology transfer activities, and incentives for industry-university collaboration.

Overall, by providing funding, capacity building, networking opportunities, access to expertise, and policy support, EELISA can significantly enhance the effectiveness and impact of TTOs in European universities, ultimately contributing to the promotion of innovation, economic growth, and societal impact across the continent.

3. Developing Efficient Technology Transfer Processes

Intellectual Property Rights (IP) Management

- Examination of best practices for managing IP rights in academia-business collaborations
- Recommendations for optimizing IP management to facilitate technology transfer

Knowledge Mining

- Strategies for identifying and extracting valuable knowledge from academic research for commercialization
- Tools and methodologies for effective knowledge mining in technology transfer processes

Skills-Expertise-Infrastructure as Services

- Analysis of the role of skills, expertise, and infrastructure in facilitating technology transfer
- Proposals for providing these resources as services to enhance collaboration between academia and industry

4.3 Intellectual Property Rights (IP) Management

Connecting Intellectual Property Rights Management to Learning Outcomes

The chapter on Intellectual Property (IP) Rights Management is integral to developing comprehensive learning outcomes that prepare students for successful industrial and entrepreneurial careers. Understanding IP rights management is crucial in today's innovation-driven economy, where protecting innovations, navigating patent laws, and leveraging intellectual assets strategically are key competencies for emerging engineers and entrepreneurs.

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The synthesis of information gathered through consultations, surveys, and collaborative discussions among EELISA partners within this chapter helps shape and refine the learning outcomes of educational programs. By analyzing current practices, challenges, and successes in IP management across diverse institutional frameworks, the consortium has identified essential skills and knowledge areas that students need to master to become adept at managing IP in their future careers.

Emphasizing IP rights within the learning outcomes ensures that students gain a solid understanding of the importance of IP in the commercial success of technological innovations and entrepreneurial ventures. For instance, through this chapter’s insights, educational programs can incorporate specific outcomes such as:

- **Understanding IP Frameworks:** Students will learn about different types of intellectual property, including patents, copyrights, trademarks, and trade secrets, and the contexts in which they are applicable.
- **Navigational Skills:** Courses can be designed to help students navigate complex IP landscapes, teaching them how to file patents, the importance of patent searches, and how to avoid infringement.
- **Strategic IP Management:** Students will be equipped with strategies to manage IP effectively, including how to make decisions about when and what to patent, how to license technologies, and how to negotiate IP terms in business deals.
- **Commercialization of IP:** Integrating knowledge on how to transform IP into viable commercial products, which is crucial for entrepreneurial success. This includes learning about market analysis, business planning, and funding strategies related to new technologies.

Furthermore, the information from this chapter aids in creating targeted recommendations for curriculum enhancements that are directly linked to the demands of the industry and entrepreneurial ecosystems. For example, recognizing a gap in IP-related negotiation skills among engineering students can lead to the development of specialized modules focused on legal aspects of technology commercialization and business negotiations.

By incorporating these tailored learning outcomes into their curricula, EELISA partner universities ensure that graduates are not only technically proficient but also adept at leveraging their innovations in the marketplace through effective IP management. This approach not only enhances the employability of the graduates but also their potential to contribute innovatively and entrepreneurially to their fields, thereby driving forward the economic and technological advancements in their industries.

BME answers

BME implements an Intellectual Property Management Policy, that governs the handling of intellectual property generated within the institution. This policy extends its purview to various forms of intellectual property, including copyrightable works such as software and databases, research outcomes eligible for industrial property rights such as patents, and the utilization of trademarks. By outlining clear guidelines and procedures, this policy streamlines the management and exploitation of intellectual assets created at the BME, ensuring transparency and consistency in handling intellectual property matters.

The presentation procedure outlined in the regulations begins with the review by the individual researcher or research group leader. This involves presenting the creation to the Center for Innovation Management and Cooperation (FIEK) through an electronic interface within eight days of its completion or reaching a certain level of technological readiness (TRL 5).

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Special attention is given to avoiding premature disclosure of the industrial property solution to prevent it from becoming publicly available before securing intellectual property rights. If there's an urgent need to initiate industrial property proceedings, this should be clearly stated in the description provided by the researcher.

Furthermore, researchers have the option to offer the university an industrial property protection solution outside the scope of the regulations. If the FIEK Director deems this solution beneficial for the university, they initiate the decision-making process.

At BME the heart of the decision-making process lies the Industrial Property Protection Committee, hereafter referred to as the Committee. This body is entrusted with the responsibility of preparing and executing decisions related to intellectual property protection solutions within the university. Comprising individuals with diverse expertise, including the Intellectual Property Expert of the Center for Innovation Management and Cooperation (FIEK), faculty representatives, and nominees by the Chancellor, the Committee ensures a comprehensive evaluation of intellectual creations.

Central to the Committee's mandate is the technical assessment of intellectual property solutions, necessitating a judicious selection of members possessing the requisite expertise. Additional members may be nominated by the Dean of the relevant faculty to augment the Committee's capabilities, ensuring a holistic evaluation process. Furthermore, the Committee may invite external experts to provide insights, thereby enriching the decision-making process with diverse perspectives.

Upon receiving presentations of intellectual creations, the Committee convenes to deliberate and reach decisions within a stipulated timeframe. Preferably, decisions are made by seeking consensus; however, in the absence thereof, a majority vote determines the course of action. The Committee's decision-making process is transparent and inclusive, with due consideration given to inputs from all stakeholders, including creators and faculty representatives.

The Committee's decision reflects a balanced assessment of the intellectual property's technical and economic viability, as well as its potential for practical application and commercial exploitation.

Upon reaching a decision, the Committee communicates its verdict, detailing the proposed form of industrial property rights, anticipated benefits, conditions for practical application, and associated costs. The decision is then signed by the Committee President and disseminated to relevant stakeholders, including the rector, chancellor, researchers, and deans.

Notably, the decision-making process also accommodates urgent scenarios wherein immediate action is imperative to safeguard intellectual property rights. In such instances, the industrial property expert of the FIEK may initiate protective measures expeditiously, ensuring timely intervention to prevent potential infringements.

[It is crucial to acknowledge that participating universities may have varying financial situations and innovation potentials. For example, at BME, Innovation Management activities are carried out by a small team of four individuals operating within a tight budget. This perspective underscores the challenges faced by universities with limited resources and highlights the need for tailored support mechanisms to address their specific needs.]

Effective management of IP is crucial for facilitating technology transfer and ensuring that innovations developed within academic institutions reach the market to benefit society.

As we at BME see to optimize IP management and streamline technology transfer processes, several recommendations can be implemented:

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Adequate financial resources are essential for supporting IP management activities. Beyond covering patent application fees, the financial envelope should encompass additional costs associated with product commercialization and promotion. This includes recruiting experts in specific fields, individuals skilled in translating research outcomes into marketable products, and conducting market research. By investing in these areas, universities can enhance their capacity to effectively manage and commercialize intellectual property.

Building strong partnerships with industry players is essential for successful technology transfer. Industrial companies often view financially struggling universities as opportunities for exploitation. To shift this perception, universities must be elevated to the status of partners. While many European universities have progressed to this level independently, others still require external support. By fostering mutually beneficial relationships with industry stakeholders, universities can negotiate fair terms that balance financial considerations with the protection of intellectual property rights. This approach fosters trust and encourages industry engagement in technology transfer initiatives.

Creating a centralized platform where university inventions and software can be showcased and promoted to market players is essential for increasing awareness and facilitating technology transfer. With support from the European Union (EU) or other relevant entities, such a platform can serve as a hub for connecting academic innovations with potential industry partners. By providing a visible and accessible channel for showcasing intellectual property, this flagship platform can bridge the gap between academia and industry, facilitating collaborative opportunities and driving innovation.

ITÜ answers

The Intellectual Industrial Property Rights Unit carries out studies to determine the appropriate protection conditions for the technology/product developed by ITU academics, researchers and students, and carries out awareness-raising and information activities on the patents, utility models and designs produced.

What Do We Do?

- Evaluation of Patent/Utility Model/Design applications
- Follow-up of national & international processes of Patent/Utility Model/Design applications
- All old, current and future studies on FSMH at ITU are collected in a single center, followed and updated regularly.
- Patent portfolio management
- Conducting process and contract management negotiations with the researcher, other universities and companies
- Providing services together with the legal department regarding intellectual property issues within the scope of contracts and general cooperation protocols of joint projects developed by ITU with industry.
- Organizing promotional awareness trainings and participating in events

UPB answers

- Examination of best practices for managing IP rights in academia-business collaborations: Key focus areas include: Ownership: Clarifying IP ownership, especially with significant contributions from both parties. Licensing agreements: Establishing terms for IP use, covering royalties and exclusivity; Protection: Ensuring IP protection via patents, copyrights, trademarks, or trade secrets;

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Dispute resolution: Implementing mechanisms for resolving IP-related disputes. Confidentiality: Safeguarding exchanged confidential information. Revenue sharing: Determining revenue distribution from IP commercialization.

- Recommendations for optimizing IP management to facilitate technology transfer: Clear agreements: Drafting comprehensive agreements detailing IP ownership and responsibilities; Early discussions: Initiating IP management talks early to prevent conflicts; Flexibility: Allowing for adjustments in agreements to adapt to changing circumstances; Expert guidance: Seeking legal and IP expertise for tailored strategies; Education: Providing training on IP rights to involved parties;

Monitoring and enforcement: Implementing mechanisms to ensure compliance and enforce rights.

UPM answers

UPM has a regulation on protection of research results (Normativa sobre protección de resultados de investigación de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid). The first regulation was approved in 2005 and it was renewed in 2017. This regulation sets norms about ownership, commercialisation, management and distribution of revenues generated by the exploitation of results. The management and protection of research results is part of the activities of the Office for Research Results Transfer Activities (OTRI). Having a regulation more than a best practice, it is a must.

<https://www.upm.es/sfs/Rectorado/Legislacion%20y%20Normativa/Normativa/Normativa%20de%20Investigacion/Normativa%20protecci%C3%B3n%20resultados%20investigaci%C3%B3n.pdf>

Another good practice or better must is having standard templates for the different procedures in the framework of the protection and commercialisation of research results, such as: ownership transfer of intellectual property rights; co-ownership agreement; distribution of royalties among inventors; etc.

UPM has also an external attorney that helps the university for the management of the patent applications.

UPM's policy of distribution of royalties among inventors is very favorable for the researchers/inventors (regarding shares that the university keeps and shares for the researcher and his/her research group), compared with the internal policies applied by other institutions.

Recommendations for optimizing IP management to facilitate technology transfer

Having a internal regulation

Having a unit and experts dealing with this, supporting researchers

Easy to digest information: UPM has a dedicated webpage on IP: https://www.upm.es/propiedad_intelectual/. This page is an online manual compiling easy to digest information and FAQs about everything related to protection of research results (intellectual property rights, patents, etc.)

ITÜ answers

IP Unit organizes training at ITU to increase public awareness of managing and licensing intellectual and industrial property rights(FSMH). In addition, it offers support in technology/product development stages, including protecting and commercializing intellectual and industrial rights. TTO's IP unit builds up an up-to-date information pool about FSMH and keeps it up-to-date and provides legal and technical guidance on intellectual property issues in joint R&D projects developed by ITU.

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SNS answers

As Scuola Normale Superiore, the experience in managing IP rights in academia-business collaboration rely on the collaboration between various university in order to have a common procedure and a common proposal. This approach typically helps in finding the final and customized agreements that in any case University has to find with the various companies: the fact itself that exist a shared and standard approach on this topic among the academic institution side reduces the initial barrier with the enterprises, represented by the fact that each university and each research group in the same university have a different approach on this topic. The vice versa process (industry common approach) results relevant too. The best practice we have as SNS on this approach was done at regional level, with collaboration among Tuscany Universities and regional government but, an European guideline having the same approach, after a discussion with all the industry stakeholders, would help on this purpose.

Another important issue is related to solving IP-related disputes: a third part committee or similar, constituted both by academic and industry representatives, will help in this cases, as a judging step to consult before the standard justice process.

4.4 Knowledge Mining

In this section Partner Institutes answers were gathered about the Knowledge Mining practices of their Universities. Inputs can help develop common practices within the EELISA consortium.

Strategies for identifying and extracting valuable knowledge from academic research for commercialization

BME Answers

Strategies to identify and commercialize valuable knowledge from academic research may include personal outreach by the Technology Transfer Office to departments (we have more than 300) and faculties, as well as showcasing success stories within the university where researchers have generated significant income from intellectual property exploitation (if there is any).

However, at BME, the challenge is not the scarcity of research findings or the need for further discoveries. Instead, the primary obstacle lies in effectively capitalizing on and commercializing the existing knowledge pool.

When researchers are not adequately compensated at competitive market rates (at BME the assistant professor's gross salary approx. 950 EUR), they often seek additional employment outside of their university roles. This lack of sufficient remuneration diminishes their motivation and energy to pursue university projects vigorously, or sometimes leading them to depart from the university altogether.

Moreover, if collaborating with the university proves financially unrewarding, researchers may resort to alternative strategies, such as attempting to independently exploit their findings, such as self-developed software, operating in a “gray zone”.

Therefore, while implementing strategies like personal outreach and showcasing success stories can be beneficial, addressing the underlying issue of inadequate compensation and incentivizing researchers to engage in university projects more actively is crucial for unlocking the full potential of intellectual property at BME.

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Tools and methodologies for effective knowledge mining in technology transfer processes face a fundamental challenge: limited financial resources often require universities to make rapid decisions regarding the viability of research results and their long-term investment potential.

Our experience at BME suggests that immediate engagement with industrial partners following a patent application is essential to gauge market demand for the invention.

Additionally, experimental research may need to be tailored to meet market development needs. To facilitate this process, establishing an interface where large companies can articulate challenges and universities can propose solutions in exchange for a success fee would be beneficial.

It's important to ensure that these collaborations do not involve the outright purchase of university intellectual property rights or research results by the company, but rather entail long-term royalty payments. This approach fosters sustainable partnerships and equitable value distribution between universities and industry stakeholders.

ITÜ answers

Istanbul Technical University is in a key position to evaluate commercial opportunities and convert them into commercial gains. Istanbul Technical University supports its academicians in extracting intellectual property from academic research, articles and thesis studies that carry commercial value.

In the first stage, the university identifies information with commercial value; in the next stage, commercially valuable information leads to the conversion of a product or service into commercial value.

Istanbul Technical University's Commercialization Unit helps identify valuable information in academic research using the following criteria. Examining the visual above, it can be seen that the number of ITU Commercialized Technologies is increasing. You can examine it from the web address. <https://haber.itu.edu.tr/haberdetay/2024/04/26/itu-ticarilestirme-sampiyonu-universiteler-arasinda-3-sirada>

Tools and methodologies for effective knowledge mining in technology transfer processes

UPM answers

As explained in the survey completed in March 2024 as well as in the different documents sent as input for D6.2 and D6.1, UPM has a complete and very varied set of tools for identifying and extracting valuable knowledge from academic research for commercialization.

A) HAVING EXPERT TEAMS AND SPECIALIZED UNITS supporting knowledge mining in its different phases. UPM TTO is made of two units: the Centre for Support for Technological Innovation (CAIT, by its Spanish acronym) and the Office for Research Results Transfer Activities (OTRI, by its Spanish acronym). The aim of CAIT UPM is precisely support knowledge mining „to help detecting high potential ideas, technologies and entrepreneurs, educating UPM community in innovation and entrepreneurship and creating high growth potential companies at UPM’s community”. Additionally, UPM OTRI is made of the following units:

Unit “Intellectual and Industrial Property”

Unit “Commercialization of R&D results” (commercialisation agreements, patents)

Unit “Scientific Culture”

Unit “University-Industry Chairs”

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Unit "Public-Private Partnerships", including industrial doctorates

OTRI Network-Indicator

Regarding tools, we can mention:

B) VISIBILITY, DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION: EASY-TO-ACCESS INFORMATION FOR RESEARCHERS. Having all the information, policies, relevant rules, etc. available on line in easily accesible formats is key. E.g. wepage of UPM's unite for protection of results: <https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/OTRI/Propiedad%20Intelectual%20e%20Industrial>, which has several sub-pages:

- Page compiling all info on rules and legislation: <https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/OTRI/Propiedad%20Intelectual%20e%20Industrial/Normativa%20de%20la%20UPM%20y%20legislaci%C3%B3n%20vigente>

- Page compiling information about patents

<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/OTRI/Propiedad%20Intelectual%20e%20Industrial/Documentaci%C3%B3n%20necesaria%20para%20la%20protecci%C3%B3n%20de%20resultados>

UPM has an independet dedicated wepage: https://www.upm.es/propiedad_intelectual/. This page is an online manual compiling easy to digest information and FAQs about everything related to protection of research results (intellectual propoperty rights, patents, etc.)

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Unidad de Propiedad Intelectual e Industrial

La Unidad de Propiedad Intelectual e Industrial se encarga de la protección de los resultados investigación generados por la comunidad universitaria para favorecer su transferencia al sector productivo. Entre sus funciones se encuentran:

- Gestión de patentes
- Asesoramiento en cuestiones relativas a propiedad intelectual e industrial
- Registro de obras de propiedad intelectual con carácter técnico (programas de ordenador, bases de datos, obras multimedia)
- Gestión de marcas institucionales
- Formación sobre propiedad intelectual e industrial

*Observatorio de
I+D+i sobre patentes*

*Normativa y
Legislación*

*¿Estás interesado en
proteger una tecnología?*

*Promoción de la
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C) COMPETITIONS TO HELP IDENTIFY IDEAS AND HELP THEM GROW INTO PRODUCTS, SERVICES, COMPANIES, e.g. UPM2T is a 10-weeks online programme that aims to support researchers and high-tech entrepreneurs on their way to validate a successful business based on technology or -actúaupm business model competition. It is key that competitions take place on a regular basis or fixed calendar.

D) Digital MARKETPLACE showcasing the technological offer. Developing and having online marketplaces is a good way of boosting the commercialisation of results. In this regard, UPM Digital Innovation Hub is an online marketplace compiling UPM's technological offer (infrastructures, equipment, technological services): <https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/>. UPM's Digital Innovation Hub has been key for building EELISA infrastructure catalogue: <https://infrastructure.eelisa.eu/>

E) Relational capital: participating and being member of associations, clusters, networks, associations, etc. is also key for supporting Knowledge Mining and commercialisation of results, including the EIT KICs. E.g. UPM is member of EIT Climate-KIC, EIT Digital-KIC, EIT Health-KIC, EIT Raw materials-KIC, EIT Urban Mobility-KIC.

UPM regularly organises a networking events called WIT (acronym for technology innovation workshops) together with companies and researchers. Each WIT focuses on a specif topic, e.g. we regularly organise a WIT on heathcare supported by Pfize Foundation (<https://www.fundacionpfizer.org/innovacion/wit-salud>).

D) OTHER INSTRUMENTS:

- Industrial chairs. Industry-University Chairs (I-U Chairs) are strategic and long term (plurennial) partnerships between companies/institutions and the University in order to carry out education, research and knowledge transfer activities in an area of common interest.

- Unidades Conjuntas Investigación (Joint Research Units). Joint research unit refers to a research unit from a legal public or private entity that wants to develop its research activity together with a UPM research structure (research group, centre or institute) for a period of three years. Joint Research Units allow external entities to set up a steady research relationship with UPM research

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structures, without the need of a creating joint research center. Researchers from the external entity are acknowledged and get the recognition as “Collaborating Research Staff” at UPM.

- DIH AIR4S. Digital Innovation Hubs are per definition a tech transfer tool. In fact, as far as UPM sees it, the structure of a DIH is what WP6 defines as a science park. A detailed description of the AIR4S can be found in UPM contribution to D5.1.

E) TRAINING. Providing training at all levels (from graduate students to senior researchers) is a key instruments „for extracting valuable knowledge from academic research for commercialization”. For instance, one of the key action lines of UPM’s DIH AIR4S is training. Please check the input sent to SSSA regarding AIR4S. Excerpt from the document:

„One key action is the organisation of training and information sessions on EU and international funding sources, with the aim of improving participant’s skills and knowledge on the opportunities offered by different programmes for funding their AI and robotic projects, how to build successful proposals under different programmes (Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, Invest EU). Here a couple of examples of the sessions organized:

Cascade Funding opportunities in the field of artificial intelligence, data and robotics (here1 and here2).

Innovation opportunities under Horizon Europe: European Innovation Council.

Digital Europe: opportunities for SMEs and start-ups (here3)

European Partnerships: opportunities for SMEs and start-ups (here4)

Additionally, AIR4S provides ad-hoc advice and support services to SMEs and start-ups on: funding opportunities (grant scan, connection with private investors), matchmaking with researchers and other stakeholders, international networking and identification of ideas”.

Training in innovation and entrepreneurship is one key mission of the EIT (European Institute of Innovation and Technology) and its KICs (Knowledge Innovation Communities). UPM is member of EIT Climate-KIC, EIT Digital-KIC, EIT Health-KIC, EIT Raw materials-KIC, EIT Urban Mobility-KIC.

ITÜ answers

Istanbul Technical University’s Commercialization Unit plays a key role in uncovering this potential and converting it into commercial value. The Unit helps extract commercially valuable information and findings from academic research using data mining tools and methodologies.

ITU, one of Turkey’s most prestigious universities with a 250-year history, carries out many important research projects and makes new discoveries each year. Many of these projects have commercial potential.

Data Mining Tools and Methodologies Used by ITU:

¹ <https://eventos.upm.es/88300/detail/oportunidades-de-cascade-funding-en-el-ambito-de-la-inteligencia-artificial-datos-y-robotica.html>

² <https://eventos.upm.es/99151/detail/oportunidades-de-cascade-funding.html>

³ <https://eventos.upm.es/90929/detail/programa-digital-europe-oportunidades-para-pymes-y-startups.html>

⁴ <https://www.air4s.eu/webinar-los-partnerships-en-el-contexto-europeo/>

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Use of Technology Analysis Platforms: Espacenet, trademap, Googlepatents, patsnap, and patbase applications can be used to analyze information in research papers, patents, and other text documents.

Data Mining: It can be used to discover patterns and relationships from experimental data and other datasets.

Machine Learning: It is used to automatically learn from data and make predictions. In particular, recent artificial intelligence applications are being used.

UPB answers

Strategies for identifying and extracting valuable knowledge from academic research for commercialization: Fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and market alignment, analyzing patents, scouting technology, and forming industry partnerships optimize knowledge extraction for commercialization.

- Tools and methodologies for effective knowledge mining in technology transfer processes: Text mining and Natural Language Processing extract insights from academic literature and patents, aiding in identifying commercialize potential trends. Data analytics analyzes datasets for valuable knowledge. Machine learning predicts research potential, while knowledge graphs visualize connections. Collaborative filtering suggests collaborations and available funding sources.

SNS answers

Knowledge mining in academia represents a crucial point to address. As SNS we have experienced various strategies but non one was a benchmark. The main point is to create an entrepreneurship in the researcher communities: typically the researchers with the right entrepreneurship culture are the best ones able to see the impact of their research on the society and therefore on the commercialization of their research. We experienced an activity of „scouting” on research activities having possible commercial applications, with a „knowledge transfer manager” specifically funded by a national funded project, but probably developing new AI tools at European level would helps in mining publications and patents having potential from this point of view, creating as a results connections between academia and industry and opening channels of collaboration on a possible commercialization.

4.5 Skills-Expertise-Infrastructure as Services

In this section Partner Institutes answers were gathered about Skills-Expertise-Infrastructure as Services of their Universities. Inputs can help develop common practices within the EELISA consortium.

Analysis of the role of skills, expertise, and infrastructure in facilitating technology transfer

BME answers

In an ideal scenario, TTO employees would possess not only the requisite expertise but also a robust utilization mindset. Merely having theoretical knowledge is insufficient; practical experience and insights from the competitive landscape are indispensable. Ideally, TTO colleagues would have founded 1-2 startups themselves, gaining firsthand experience of the ramifications of poor decisions, delayed responses, and the frustrations of negative market feedback. They would also understand the challenges of devising new development strategies based on fresh market research findings and

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the resilience required to rebound from setbacks. Given that many researchers may lack this level of determination, it falls upon the TTO to exemplify it.

As long as internal resources do not suffice, acquiring such experience may necessitate seeking external expertise, akin to investing in team-building training and market research.

Similarly, in an optimal situation universities would possess comprehensive software for patent research, another for market analysis, contract templates for utilization agreements, and guidelines for intellectual property valuation.

Under such circumstances, financing various association memberships, as well as participation in international fairs and conferences, would not pose any challenges, as funds could be allocated from the budget designated for intellectual property maintenance.

In the realm of facilitating technology transfer, the interplay of skills, expertise, and infrastructure plays a pivotal role, reminiscent of the age-old Hungarian adage, "a successful war requires money, horses, and weapons." While the importance of "money" (financial resources) has been underscored on multiple occasions, delving into the significance of skills and infrastructure sheds light on the comprehensive nature of the endeavor.

In this context, the "horses" symbolize the technological environment, encompassing the physical spaces conducive to fostering innovation. This includes dedicated areas for training researchers, mentoring startup teams, hosting competitions, and facilitating international collaborations. Such spaces serve as the breeding ground for innovation, providing the necessary resources such as location facilities, equipment, catering services, and access to renowned speakers.

Meanwhile, the "weapons" represent the amalgamation of complex knowledge and expertise within the organization. This entails a robust arsenal of internal product management skills, complemented by a deep understanding of legal and economic frameworks relevant to technology transfer. Moreover, adept project management capabilities are essential for orchestrating the various facets of technology transfer initiatives effectively.

The synergy of these elements becomes increasingly apparent as more innovative research results emerge. With a growing number of projects, the demand for resources - whether financial, infrastructural, or expertise - intensifies, emphasizing the necessity of a multifaceted approach to technology transfer.

The provision of resources as a service to enhance collaboration between academia and industry is a multifaceted endeavor, requiring a nuanced understanding of both resource nature and accessibility. Across the EU, universities face varying circumstances and challenges when entering the market, shaped by factors such as national market size and regional economic landscapes. For instance, while entering the American or Far Eastern market poses significant hurdles (the challenges may differ based on geographical location and market dynamics) for spinoffs from any EU country.

To address these complexities, a multi-level service model could be implemented. Firstly, leveraging the expertise of Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) from partner universities or involving appointed country-specific experts could provide tailored advice and support for navigating local markets. These experts would offer insights and guidance relevant to their respective countries, helping academia and industry partners overcome market entry barriers effectively.

Furthermore, establishing dedicated support teams focused on penetrating distant markets, such as the US or Canada, would be essential. Market entry strategies for these regions differ substantially

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from those in European markets, necessitating specialized approaches and expertise. Collaborative efforts with universities and institutions from other continents, engaged in partnerships with specific universities, could offer invaluable insights and assistance in this regard.

Another avenue for enhancing collaboration is the identification and connection of complementary projects or research potentials. Utilizing tools like the BME competence map, which provides a comprehensive overview of institutional competencies (<https://competence.bme.hu/>), TTOs could identify synergies and opportunities for collaboration. For example, BME's innovation in recycling degraded PET waste for high-quality plastic production could align with projects at other universities focusing on environmentally conscious solutions or waste management. By sharing projects on a common interface and seeking connections, TTOs can facilitate cross-institutional collaboration and maximize the impact of innovative initiatives.

ITÜ answers

Mechanisms for Transforming Important Inventions Developed at ITU into Industrial Applications and Bringing Them to Society

Various mechanisms are used to transform important inventions developed at ITU into industrial applications and bring them to society. The primary mechanism is the "Technology Commercialization Process."

Technology Commercialization Process at ITU

The Technology Commercialization Process at ITU is carried out under the umbrella of the ITU Projects and Commercialization Management Office. This process aims to transform new technologies developed by researchers into usable products and services in the industrial field. The ITU Projects and Commercialization Office carries out the processes through interfaces such as ITU 1773 Teknopark, ITU 1773 TTO, and ITÜNOVA Technology Transfer Office.

- The Technology Commercialization Process Includes the Following Steps:
- Identification of Inventions and Patent Application: Innovative inventions developed by ITU academics and researchers are protected by applying to the Intellectual Property Rights Unit of the ITU Projects Office. ITU has 350 different patented technologies in its portfolio. At this stage, ITU employs expert patent specialists and technology transfer professionals in their field.
- Patent Evaluation and Determination of Commercialization Potential: The Commercialization Unit of the Istanbul Technical University Projects Office manages the evaluation of patented technologies and the determination of their commercialization potential. Market research and competitive analysis are conducted at this stage.
- Licensing and Collaborations: Technologies that are successful in the Patent Commercialization Process are commercialized through licensing agreements with industrial partners. Collaborations ensure that technologies are quickly brought to market. Istanbul Technical University has transferred 28 different technologies to industry through licensing, assignment, and usage agreements between 2016 and 2024.
- Entrepreneurship and Technology Transfer: ITU encourages the commercialization of projects developed by students and academics by providing support in entrepreneurship and technology transfer.

UPB answers

- Analysis of the role of skills, expertise, and infrastructure in facilitating technology transfer:

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Skills and Expertise: Technology transfer requires a range of abilities, including scientific, business, and legal know-how; Scientific and Technical Proficiency: Understanding the technology being transferred; Business Skills: Market analysis, business modeling, and negotiation; Legal Knowledge: Contract drafting, licensing, and IP laws.

Infrastructure: Adequate resources, both physical and digital, i.e. Evaluation of Existing Infrastructure: Assessing availability and accessibility; Gap Identification: Pinpointing deficiencies;

Resource Optimization: Enhancing efficiency.

- Proposals for providing these resources as services to enhance collaboration between academia and industry: Skill Development: Training researchers, entrepreneurs, and professionals in tech transfer through workshops and online courses covering IP management, market analysis, and negotiation; Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs): Establishing TTOs in academia to provide expertise in IP, licensing, and collaborations with industry; Incubators and Accelerators: Creating facilities supporting academic startups with labs, mentoring, and funding; Public-Private Partnerships: Collaborating among academia, industry, and government to invest in tech transfer infrastructure and talent; Technology Transfer Networks: Establishing consortia to share resources and expertise among academia, industry, and transfer professionals.

SNS answers

The expertise necessary to TT are both technical, as legal and economical. The ideal TT manager knows also the industry side, the production processes and their request from commercialization of products. To merge all these skills a TT staff results necessary together with a strict collaboration and knowledge of the research activities in the single research group.

Proposals for providing these resources as services to enhance collaboration between academia and industry

ITÜ answers

Recommendations for Enhancing Technology Commercialization at Universities

- The experiences gained from ITU's Technology Commercialization Process can serve as a valuable guide for other universities and relevant public institutions. We recommend the following:
- Establishment of Technology Commercialization Offices: Each university should be encouraged to establish a Technology Commercialization Office, such as ITU Projects and Commercialization Office, ITU 1773 Technology Transfer Office, Technopark and Entrepreneurship Centers, to provide guidance and support to researchers in commercializing their inventions.
- Development of Patent Portfolios: Universities should encourage their researchers to patent their inventions and build a strong patent portfolio.
- Creation of Industrial Collaboration Platforms: Universities should create platforms, such as fairs, conferences, and joint research projects, to promote collaboration with industrial organizations.
- Development of Entrepreneurial Culture: Universities should develop an entrepreneurial culture by providing entrepreneurship training and mentoring services to students and researchers.
- Government Support: In Turkey, TUBITAK, an institution utilized by universities and industrialists, provides financial support for the production of high-tech products. Universities

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particularly benefit from the TUBITAK 1702 Patent Licensing call on the commercialization side. Governments can provide tools such as financing, tax incentives, and legal regulations to support the technology commercialization activities of universities.

SNS answers

Increase the TT personnel, that typically results understaffed; disseminate research teams of staff liaison to TT offices and provide training for researchers on entrepreneurship issues; organize events like FAIR, workshop etc. where academia and industries could meet; co-fund projects dedicated to academia-industry collaboration on TT; increase the PhD positions having as research project also the collaboration with SMEs; support TT office networks among the various partners.

4.6 Institutional Good Practices of Technology Transfer

4.6.1 Case Studies of Successful Technology Transfer Initiatives

Examination of exemplary technology transfer projects within partner institutions

BME answers

Currently mentored startups (39):

On the English and Hungarian startup management course we support 8 beginner startup teams. From the previous years (under the umbrella of Z10) 4 scale-up startups (Rollin, Respary, Aeri, Fastrrr) remained near the BME and are renting office spaces on the 8th floor, plus shared desks and Fablab access.

We support also 4 early-MVP stage teams from the Cross University program and during the preparation phase of the Danube Cup, we coached 16 teams.

In the HSUP program, there are 11 teams from BME with whom we have ongoing support activities

Spinoffs created or supported by the university (4):

To respond to the reluctant request of the government as the main financing authority to the BME, in 2023 4 spinoffs were created:

iMotionDrive | <https://imotiondrive.com>

DriveByCloud | <https://drivebycloud.com>

Beton CT | <https://www.aut.bme.hu/Pages/Research/BetonCT>

AHUD

https://www.bme.hu/news/20240208/The_Future_is_Now_Physicist_Engineer_Training_at_BME?language=en

Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programs and Courses

To deliver up-to-date trending and in practice proven knowledge and experiences the Centre for Innovation Management and Cooperation and the BME Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences in mutual organization offer courses incorporating entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial skill learning, as well as practical classes, from entry-academia level up until MBA graduation., such as :

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-> Initiation and Management of Innovative Ventures (IMIV) - 1 semester (14 weeks)

Theoretical course about methods and best practices in the scope of early-stage intrapreneurship and entrepreneurship businesses and project conceptualizations, professional validation methods, and business and/or investment-focused pitch presentations. Available in: Hungarian

(based on participation from entrepreneur-in-residence as lecturers and mentors, and various ecosystem players) Since 2011 Cca. 130 participants/semester

-> Startup management (SM) - 1 semester (14 weeks)

Practical workshop course of IMIV – A specially dedicated mentor lead workshop program, for the practical implementation of the theoretical learnings from IMIV. Available in Hungarian and English

(based on participation from entrepreneur-in-residence as lecturers and mentors, and various ecosystem players) Since 2011 Cca. 40 participants/semester

-> Business/Enterprise development specialization at the MBA - 2 semesters (24 - 26 weeks)
Available in Hungarian

As part of a 2-year education program, the Faculty offers the possibility to select intra/entrepreneurship specialization, where experienced managers and professionals learn the top new methods in the field of launching & managing a business, executing real validation, delivering business documents for approval and fundraising, in a team project form, and learn also to successfully pitch their project.

Available in Hungarian Cca. 45 participants/semester

-> HIH Cross-university program sponsored by the National Bank of Hungary - 1 semester (14 weeks) Available in Hungarian (closing pitch in English)

A tailor-made course based on (IMIV and SM) courses of BME, for students of 3 different universities in Hungary, with 2 special one-day side events, where entrepreneurs and ecosystem players are invited to give a speech and/or workshop on various topics related to entrepreneurship. Selected startup projects at the closure get monetary prizes and receive one-year-long incubation support.

Available in: Hungarian Since 2023 Cca. 100 participants/semester

-> Hungarian Startup University Program (HSUP) - 1+1 semester (24 - 26 weeks)

Created by the Hungarian Innovation Agency, a subsidiary of The National Research, Development, and Innovation Office, this program offers basic knowledge about startup ventures via an online learning tool and fosters the creation of project teams, selected randomly from across university students participating in this program. In the second semester, teams need to develop the pre-selected idea and demonstrate their findings in a summary, to obtain further financial support to launch it.

Available in: Hungarian Since 2020 Cca. 40 participants/semester

Incubation Centers and Start-up Support

In 2020 the Centre for Innovation Management and Cooperation with the government's financial support launched the BME Z10 incubator, which lasted until 2022 and created an 800sqm environment for 10 startups.

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In 2023 the closer cooperation between the Centre for Innovation Management and Cooperation and the BME Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences, and based on the conclusions from the Z10 incubator journey a new direction has been decided, under the name of BME University Spinoff Startup Studio - BME U[S]3.

BME U[S]3 is not simply hosting most of the entrepreneurial/intrapreneurial courses of BME but furthermore, it has become an inspiring environment for entre- and intrapreneurship-related events and programs, a starting junction for spinoffs and startups to receive legal, IP, business-development, and professional validation support and mentoring, accumulating into business growth. As an extension for the grant management and industry cooperation activities of the Centre for Innovation Management and Cooperation, BME U[S]3, is bringing closer ecosystem players – until now unreachable– to BME.

Hackathons and Innovation Challenges

-> Business Express Program (5 weeks) | intensive business development-focused workshop and lecture series for spinoff and startup projects from and outside of the university

-> Danube Cup | International (and National) Pitch competition event for early-stage, validation-backed idea solutions created by students from 9 – in the Danube Region residing – Universities (DE-HUN-A-SRB)

-> AI Pitch Competition | Open pitch competition for AI/ML solutions created by students, researchers, and SMEs from the local ecosystems around the BME

Industry Partnerships and Networking Events:

The 8 faculty of BME regularly organize partnership and networking events between industry players and academia students, researchers. Several cooperations have been launched in the past and recently, the university has published its competence map, to publicly furthermore support these cooperations.

See: <https://competence.bme.hu/>

ITÜ answers

Evaluation of Istanbul Technical University DEFİNEX / Patent Commercialization Process:

A meeting was held with Prof. Dr. Oğuzhan KÜLEKÇİ, a computer science academic from Istanbul Technical University's Informatics Institute, to evaluate the European Patent Office-registered patent titled "METHODS AND ALGORITHMS TO BE DEVELOPED FOR BIG DATA MANAGEMENT, MULTIMEDIA DATA TRANSMISSION AND BLOCKCHAIN STUDIES AIMED AT DATA PRIVACY AND SECURITY." The patent was evaluated and the commercialization process was initiated.

Considering criteria such as the remaining patent life, prototype level, mass production cost, and countries where protection is requested, DEFİNEX was contacted, and a transfer agreement was signed on June 1, 2022. DEFİNEX undertook to pay a transfer fee of 900,000 TL. Work packages were determined together with DEFİNEX, including patent review and coding, patent application and design, configuration and implementation of targeted applications, and commercialization phases.

The project "DEVELOPMENT OF CODING AND ALGORITHMS FOR DATA PRIVACY AND SECURITY, MULTIMEDIA DATA TRANSMISSION AND BLOCKCHAIN APPLICATIONS" was supported by TÜBİTAK, Turkey's funding institution, by 65%. DEFİNEX paid the first installment of 450,000 TL on October 10, 2022. Payments were shared between Mukit (70%), ITU (20%), and

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ITÜNOVA TTO (10%). The patent was transferred to DEFİNEX, generating 900,000 TL in revenue, and DEFİNEX began to develop products with the patent. ITU has successfully completed the commercialization process for 27 different patents similar to the shared example.

UPB answers

POLITEHNICA Bucharest research activities are amongst the top priorities of the university with two of the most important research hubs in the region – The Research Center for Advanced Materials, Products, and Processes - CAMPUS and the Research Center for Intelligent Products, Processes and Services – PRECIS (<https://international.upb.ro/on-campus/research-and-science>).

One good example of technology transfer projects is coming from 5G Lab Research Group (<https://futurenetworks.upb.ro/research-projects/>), important being the three private funded R&D projects (approx. 35000 EUR without VAT) with several components:

5G and LoRa R&D development

For this project the lab team implemented several end-to-end 5G and LoRa systems for a private company

Tech Transfer evaluation and recommendations

- For this project the lab team assessed the tech transfer capabilities of the company and proposed several measures through which the tech transfer process to be more straight forward.
- Testing 5G off-the shelf devices
- For this task the team developed and implemented a test-bed in a home-like environment, to be used to test the capacity of the devices in a real environment. Using the designed environment several capacity/traffic/bandwidth tests were performed
- Testing LTE-m network and LTE-m network parameters for IoT devices
- For this task the team performed several test (mobility/static/power saving) to demonstrate what are the optimal parameters to be set on an IoT device in order to be optimized for the network.
- The project current results were used by the industry partner to launch new products.
- Identification of key factors contributing to their success

The key factors contributing to their success is the market / demand oriented approach, synthesized in their scientific / technological offer (<https://futurenetworks.upb.ro/future-industry-collaboration/>):

The Future Networks 5G lab offers the following services:

- End-to-End Testing and validating 5G scenarios/solutions for different verticals
- Prototype 5G application on different market verticals
- Prototype 5G/6G algorithms for different use-cases
- Security Assessment for 5G applications/services/networks
- Security Implementation for 5G networks
- Implement different use-cases for 5G/5G+/6G applications
- Research and development of 5G+/6G networks/applications/services
- 5G/6G Consultancy for public and private stakeholders
- Business consultancy for scaling up startups or spinoffs
- Participation as partners in national and international R&D and innovation projects for cybersecurity and 6G

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SNS answers

As SNS we were impressed by JOSEPH and ZOLOHOF incubators by FAU, the training programs for students and researchers by UPM; the huge activity on start-up support by ITU. As SNS and SSSA we collaborate on a Joint Technology Transfer Office with other small Italian universities, JoTTO that helps in finding a common approach to TT and to Contamination lab with University of Pisa, where students are educated to have also an entrepreneurial approach to their study and research activities.

Identification of key factors contributing to their success

UPM answers

UPM Thematic Communities were put in place by UPM in 2018 with the objective of boosting connections between highly specialised UPM structures coming from different research areas, thus creating research and innovation interdisciplinary spaces. The objectives of UPM Thematic Communities were:

- To create research and innovation interdisciplinary spaces, additional and complementary to the traditional highly specialized structures (research centers, research groups);
- To align research and innovation with sustainable development goals (SDGs) and help address current complex societal and industrial challenges;
- To boost connections among UPM research structures from different research areas;
- To boost connections with external stakeholders, both public authorities and the industry at local, regional, national and international level, and thus reinforcing the ecosystem.

UPM Thematic Communities have been a very successful initiative that has met all the aforementioned aims, this is, to create new interdisciplinary spaces to address current complex societal challenges. Given its applied interdisciplinary nature and the fruitful collaborations born out of the communities, which includes industry and other external stakeholders, UPM Thematic Communities can be considered a successful tech transfer initiative.

A key success factor for the communities has been the support given for its creation: the setting up of communities was supported under an internal call, where communities received funding for hiring a facilitator. The role of the facilitator has been fundamental.

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ITÜ

Key Factors in ITU's Commercialization Success:

ITU's commercialization success can be attributed to the following key factors:

Right Patent Selection:

Istanbul Technical University selected a patent with high commercialization potential and marketability. The patent focuses on a current and important area such as data privacy and security, multimedia data transmission, and blockchain. After this analysis, ITU Commercialization focused on the commercialization of this patent.

Comprehensive Evaluation:

A detailed evaluation was conducted considering criteria such as the remaining life of the patent, prototype level, mass production cost, and countries where protection is requested. This clearly identified the commercial potential and risks of the patent.

Right Company Selection:

DEFINEX was selected as a company experienced and competent in developing and marketing products related to the patent. DEFINEX's belief in the patent technology and its resources for commercialization played a significant role in the project's success.

Effective Work Package Selection:

Clear and comprehensive work packages were defined, including patent review and coding, patent application and design, configuration and implementation of targeted applications, and

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commercialization phases. This allowed the project to be carried out in a planned manner and completed on time.

TUBITAK Support from Türkiye:

TÜBİTAK's support for 65% of the project contributed to the provision of financial resources and the sustainability of the project.

Sharing Model:

The fair sharing of payments between the Inventors (70%), ITU (20%), and ITÜNOVA TTO (10%) increased motivation and participation among all project stakeholders.

Experience and Knowledge Accumulation:

Istanbul Technical University's experience and knowledge in successfully completing the commercialization process of 27 different patents played a significant role in the success of this project as well.

Istanbul Technical University's success in the patent commercialization process is attributed to factors such as right patent selection, comprehensive evaluation, right partner selection, effective work packages, TÜBİTAK support, fair sharing model, and experience and knowledge accumulation.

SNS answers

Clear identification of the key factors contributing to the TT process in similar contexts, creation of a culture of innovation in the research environment starting from the PhD students, the strength of networking on finding solutions to innovation problems, funding from industries and VC, connection between research and SMEs.

4.6.2 Lessons Learned and Best Practices

BME answers

One key lesson learned is the critical importance of resource allocation. In resource-poor environments, prioritizing research results and inventions early on becomes imperative, especially when their market potential is uncertain. Without sufficient resources, even the most promising innovations may languish.

Another important lesson is the significance of industry connections. Attempting to engage market players or manufacturers without established industry contacts is often futile. Cold calls rarely yield results, highlighting the necessity of robust industry networks for successful technology transfer endeavors.

Disparities in funding between universities also emerge as a significant factor. Institutions with larger state funding enjoy greater resources and may even have their own venture capital to support spinoffs and startups. This disparity underscores the need for equitable resource distribution to foster innovation across all academic institutions.

The composition of innovation councils within universities (at least at BME) also plays a crucial role. While these councils typically comprise individuals with experience in large companies, their perspective may not fully align with that of spinoff founders. Understanding the unique challenges faced by spinoff founders is essential for fostering effective collaboration between researchers and universities.

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Moreover, the bureaucratic hurdles within university systems often hinder fast-paced innovation. Lengthy procurement processes and contract negotiations can stifle close-to-market activities, highlighting the need for streamlined procedures conducive to agile decision-making.

Shifting organizational mindsets towards utilization rather than solely academic progress is another key lesson. Embracing a utilization-oriented approach requires a fundamental shift in thinking, which may necessitate targeted training and fostering curiosity and interest among stakeholders.

In summary, synthesizing lessons from institutional experiences underscores the importance of resource allocation, industry connections, equitable funding, tailored support structures, streamlined processes, and a shift towards utilization-focused mindsets to facilitate effective technology transfer within academic institutions.

UPM answers

Setting the value of a technology as a challenge. One challenge to be highlighted is how much a technology can be sold for, i.e. setting the value of a technology. It is always a tricky part. If the technology is at very early stage, there are few evidences regarding its application and therefore its value.

ITÜ answers

Setting the value of a technology as a challenge. One challenge to be highlighted is how much a technology can be sold for, i.e. setting the value of a technology. It is always a tricky part. If the technology is at very early stage, there are few evidences regarding its application and therefore its value.

As the Commercialization Unit of Istanbul Technical University, our goal is to evaluate the inventions produced by the university in terms of their commercial potential and to transform these inventions into real products. The ITU Commercialization Unit collaborates with ITU 1773 Technopark, ITU 1773 Technology Transfer Office, and ITU GINOVA. Additionally, environmental, material, information, and electronic technologies are among the strongest areas in ITU's patent portfolio. ITU holds 350 different patented technologies in its portfolio and actively participates in the evaluation and commercialization process of patents.

Between 2016 and 2023, the ITU Projects Office Commercialization Unit successfully transferred 27 different patented technologies to the industry through licensing. The challenges encountered in Istanbul Technical University's commercialization processes directly affect the institution's experience, the characteristics of the developed technologies, and market conditions. For example, the inability to effectively share patented technologies with relevant companies or to establish licensing agreements can lead to low revenue generation. Despite the low awareness of patents and patenting in Turkey, Istanbul Technical University has sufficient experience in determining the correct commercialization model, conducting negotiations with potential licensees, and obtaining the deserved license revenue for the institution.

The university values university-industry collaboration stemming from its institutional culture. However, legal barriers such as intellectual property rights violations and patent disputes can result in both financial losses and damage to reputation. This situation impacts the institution's technology transfer performance and serves as an example to other universities in Turkey.

UPB answers

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POLITEHNICA Bucharest experience in technology transfer reveals a „top-down” efficient approach, when the „bottom-up” initiatives to capitalize results of applicative research are difficult to finalize because either the partners in projects are SMEs with low capacity to „enter” the market with innovative products, or TRL of the results (products, services, technologies) is low, thus difficult to reach interest for attracting investment funding. The „top-down” approach is successfully valorized in cooperation programs, such as: Romanian Artificial Intelligence HUB – HRIA (<https://upb.ro/hub-roman-de-inteligenta-artificiala-hria/>), Smart City Cluster – CITICluster (<https://citiccluster.upb.ro/>), AI CENTER UPB (<https://aiexcellence.upb.ro/partners/>), Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic – DIANA NATO (<https://diana.nato.int/about-diana.html>), INNOVATIONS LABS (<https://www.innovationlabs.ro/whoweare>).

SNS answers

It is a very hard work to do that requires a lot of effort both in terms of HR that in long-term projects.

As a small university we have to concentrate our top-down approaches only on very small amount and selected TT topics and actions, typically and better if they are project-driven and -supported, while bottom-up requests are always encouraged and supported by our TTO. Networking with other partners are crucial and constant training on entrepreneurial approaches to research for students is very important.

4.6.3 Development of guidelines and best practices for effective technology transfer

BME answers

The development of guidelines and best practices for effective technology transfer is essential for optimizing collaboration and innovation among academic institutions. Within this framework, it's crucial to acknowledge the varying levels of advancement among participating entities. Some universities are in a significantly more advanced phase of innovation, characterized by a higher number of patent applications, software developments, and utilization rates. These "leading" universities have accumulated extensive experience and navigated numerous challenges that newly established Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) are only beginning to encounter.

To promote collaboration rather than competition among universities, it's imperative to establish an EU-level solution. Such a solution would facilitate cooperative efforts, allowing universities to leverage each other's strengths and resources for mutual benefit.

One approach to disseminating best practices is through an online platform accessible to TTO employees. This platform could host a repository of good practices categorized by theme or keywords, enabling TTOs to learn from successful strategies implemented by their counterparts.

Practical workshops focused on pricing or price negotiation simulations could also be valuable. These workshops would provide hands-on experience and skill-building opportunities for TTO employees, enhancing their effectiveness in technology transfer activities.

Additionally, subscribing to EU-level databases containing market segment pricing information could offer valuable insights for universities seeking to commercialize their innovations. Access to typical and average prices within each market segment would aid in developing competitive pricing strategies.

The EU could further support technology transfer efforts by creating online fairs and marketplaces tailored to specific industries or market segments. These platforms would allow universities to

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showcase their projects to potential investors and industry partners, facilitating collaboration and investment opportunities.

Furthermore, EU-level support for training innovation managers could be instrumental in strengthening technology transfer capabilities across universities. Workshops, conducted on a "train the trainer" basis, could involve experienced universities sharing their expertise with those operating with limited staff, fostering knowledge exchange and capacity building in technology transfer management.

UPB answers

Technology transfer involves moving scientific knowledge and innovations from one context to another for societal benefit and economic growth: Identification: Spot technologies with potential based on commercial viability, IP status, and societal impact; Evaluation: Assess technologies using criteria like feasibility, market demand, and scalability; IP Management: Handle IP rights with strategies for protection, licensing, and negotiation; Partnership: Form strategic collaborations between research institutions, industry, and investors; Risk Management: Mitigate financial, regulatory, and market risks associated with transfer; Commercialization: Develop tailored pathways like spin-offs or licensing, informed by market analysis; Capacity Building: Provide training in IP management, entrepreneurship, and negotiation; Monitoring: Continuously monitor and evaluate transfer initiatives for progress and improvement; Ethics: Consider ethical implications and societal benefits, adhering to responsible innovation principles; Knowledge Sharing: Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange through open platforms and networks.

SNS answers

NETWORKING ON T; IP management European GUIDELINES for an effective Academic-Industry collaboration; COMMON TRAINING program on entrepreneurship for students; shared best practices on innovation, organizing common events, workshops, awards, hackathon, innovation fairs based on on a model that results effective by other partner experiences.

4.7 Recommendations to EELISA-level Co-operation in Technology Transfer

4.7.1 Strengthening Inter-Institutional Collaboration

Strategies for promoting collaboration between EELISA member institutions in technology transfer activities

BME answers

To promote cooperation between EELISA member institutions in technology transfer activities, in agreement with the previous ones, a few more strategies can be employed to foster collaboration and leverage the collective expertise and resources of participating universities.

Firstly, it's essential to map out joint research areas and identify potential areas of collaboration. Utilizing tools like the BME competence map (<https://competence.bme.hu/>), which provides insights into the expertise available at different universities, can facilitate this process. Often, researchers within the network are aware of each other's work, but the Technology Transfer Offices may lack knowledge of these connections. Establishing clear channels for communication and collaboration between TTOs can help bridge this gap and facilitate meaningful partnerships.

Another strategy is to highlight the unique skills and expertise of individuals working within the TTOs. By showcasing the capabilities of TTO staff members, institutions can identify opportunities for intra-network collaboration and resource sharing. For instance, if one university's TTO has legal expertise

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in a specific field relevant to another university's project, collaboration on legal matters can be explored. It's essential to consider mechanisms for compensation or reciprocity for such collaborations, such as "callable credits" or informal agreements.

Practical solutions for maintaining regular communication and collaboration between TTOs are also crucial. Establishing informal channels for interaction, such as joint expert chat platforms or virtual brainstorming sessions, can facilitate quick exchanges of ideas and information. These platforms should be user-friendly and accessible to encourage active participation from TTO staff.

Additionally, organizing joint events and workshops on relevant themes can provide opportunities for face-to-face interactions and relationship-building among TTOs. These events can serve as platforms for sharing best practices, discussing common challenges, and exploring potential collaborative projects in a more relaxed setting.

Overall, promoting cooperation between EELISA member institutions in technology transfer activities requires a multifaceted approach that emphasizes communication, collaboration, and the exchange of expertise and resources. By leveraging the collective strengths of participating universities, the network can enhance its capacity for innovation and technology commercialization.

UPM answers

- Having a common policy for the protection of IP rights on research results produced out of EELISA joint actions will be useful or even needed at a certain point, including a co-ownership policy/agreement and distribution of revenues policy.
- Reinforcing connections between specific TTOs experts is also needed, particularly, creating a group or reinforcing connections among expert in IPRs/patents would be good idea.
- Launching a competition focused on early-stage spin-offs and deep-tech start-ups: we had the prototype contest, but it was targeted to consumer goods and services. It might be a good idea having an EELISA competition for identifying research results ready for commercialisation (knowledge mining), but with an industrial or B2B application.
- Having an Innovation Committee, similarly to ACRI (Advisory Council on Research and Innovation) but exclusively focused on innovation.

UPB answers

Establish Collaborative Platforms: Create forums for member institution representatives to meet regularly, share best practices, discuss challenges, and explore collaboration opportunities. These platforms can be workshops, conferences, or online communities; Promote Joint Research: Encourage collaborative research projects among institutions to address challenges and develop innovative solutions, attracting industry interest; Cross-Institutional TTOs: Establish centralized TTOs serving multiple institutions, streamlining patenting, licensing, and startup support; Facilitate Exchange Programs: Enable exchanges among researchers, students, and staff to foster collaboration and share expertise in tech transfer within the network.

SNS answers

Create a common ADVISORY BOARD FOR INNOVATION and a network of TT offices; create a common web-based platform for sharing experiences and activities, also to promote collaboration among spin-off, researchers and students on innovation. Developing an AI-based tool for scouting and mining of possible application of research activities, also to stimulate our researchers on entrepreneurial approach. Create exchange projects for mobility for staff, academic, students on

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these topics. Enhance collaboration on common research projects and create innovation communities involving both staff personnel, as academic and students.

4.7.2 Standardization of Processes and Procedures

Recommendations for standardizing technology transfer processes across the EELISA network

BME answers

Standardizing technology transfer processes across the EELISA network can streamline collaboration and facilitate efficient knowledge exchange among member institutions. Here are some recommendations for standardizing these processes:

Certain elements of technology transfer processes, such as contract templates or project documentation, can be standardized by providing sample templates. These templates should serve as a starting point for negotiations and agreements while ensuring compliance with national laws and regulations.

Identify areas where standardization is feasible on an international level. This includes pricing techniques, price negotiations, and principles for valuing intellectual property. By adopting common standards in these areas, member institutions can enhance transparency and facilitate smoother transactions.

Establish a common online marketplace where member institutions can showcase their projects and innovations. Develop a standardized template for project submissions to ensure consistency and ease of access. This platform can serve as a centralized hub for networking, collaboration, and knowledge sharing.

Develop standardized training programs for preparing startup teams. These programs should cover essential topics such as business development, entrepreneurship, and innovation management. By providing consistent training across the network, member institutions can equip startup teams with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed.

Implement scholarship programs aimed at TTOs to facilitate learning and knowledge exchange between institutions. Offer opportunities for TTO staff to work at leading universities within the network, allowing them to gain insights into best practices and innovative approaches. Explore EU frameworks to support these exchange programs and address logistical challenges such as relocation for senior staff members.

Two groups of support activities are crucial for fostering an environment where technology transfer thrives. Financial assistance ensures that universities have the resources to engage in collaborative ventures and access expert guidance, while connection-building initiatives facilitate networking and knowledge exchange, paving the way for impactful collaborations and the successful commercialization of innovations.

Financial Support Activities:

- Establishing a dedicated financial support fund would address the needs of universities facing resource constraints. This fund could be utilized to cover various expenses associated with technology transfer activities, including participation in industry events, conferences, and workshops. By providing financial assistance, universities with limited budgets can actively engage in technology transfer initiatives and collaborate more effectively with other TTOs and industry partners.

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- Setting up an expert group within the EELISA network would enable universities to access specialized expertise for their technology transfer projects. Experts could offer guidance on intellectual property management, legal matters, market analysis, and business development strategies. Compensation from the EU for their time and services would ensure equitable access to valuable knowledge and facilitate smoother technology transfer processes.
- Direct EU funding specifically allocated for the maintenance and expansion of TTO offices would bolster technology transfer capabilities across member institutions. By reducing reliance on national funding sources, universities can receive consistent support for their innovation activities. This funding could be allocated based on the needs and performance of each TTO, ensuring fair distribution and maximizing impact.
- One of the pressing needs for EELISA Universities is the establishment of an EU Venture Capital initiative to provide vital financial support. Such a venture capital fund could serve as a catalyst for innovation and entrepreneurship by investing in the utilization of intellectual property generated within the EELISA network. This venture capital entity would play a crucial role in fostering the growth of startups and spinoffs emerging from these universities, providing them with the necessary financial resources to develop and commercialize their ideas. Additionally, it would help bridge the gap between academia and industry, facilitating the transition of cutting-edge research into practical applications that benefit society. Overall, an EU Venture Capital for EELISA Universities would not only stimulate economic growth and job creation but also amplify the impact of academic research on real-world challenges.

Connection-Building Initiatives:

- Creating an online marketplace for technology transfer projects would provide a centralized platform for universities to showcase their research outcomes and innovations. Large EU companies could browse through project listings and collaborate with universities on promising initiatives. Standardized templates and interfaces would streamline project submissions and facilitate communication between stakeholders, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Extending the Competence Map to all participating universities would enhance knowledge sharing and collaboration within the EELISA network. A common knowledge base with standardized interfaces and templates could serve as a repository for best practices, case studies, and success stories in technology transfer. This shared resource would enable universities to learn from each other's experiences and leverage collective expertise to overcome challenges.
- Forming an Innovation Advisory Board or Committee comprising seasoned professionals and industry experts would provide strategic guidance and mentorship to universities within the network. The advisory body could offer insights into emerging trends, market opportunities, and innovation strategies, helping universities align their technology transfer efforts with industry needs and market demands.
- Organizing networking events, joint competitions, and training programs would foster collaboration and cross-pollination of ideas among startups and spinoffs managed by TTOs. By bringing together innovators, entrepreneurs, and industry stakeholders, these initiatives would create opportunities for knowledge exchange, partnership building, and potential investment. Additionally, offering scholarships (similar to Erasmus) for promising PhD students would incentivize research commercialization and entrepreneurship, nurturing the next generation of innovators.
- Facilitating collaboration among TTO employees through workshops, joint projects, and knowledge-sharing initiatives would strengthen technology transfer capabilities across the network.

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By providing opportunities for professional development and peer learning, TTOs can enhance their expertise in intellectual property management, licensing agreements, and industry engagement. This collaborative approach would enable TTOs to deliver more effective support to researchers and facilitate successful technology transfer outcomes.

- Integrating the EELISA program with existing industrial programs and initiatives would amplify the impact of technology transfer efforts. By aligning with industry priorities and leveraging external funding opportunities, universities can enhance their competitiveness and attract investment for innovative projects. This integration would create synergies between academic research and industrial needs, driving economic growth and fostering innovation ecosystems across Europe.

UPM answers

Standardization might not be so easy to achieve, but we might be able to develop joint policies, joint instruments or joint services for JOINT ACTIONS. I.e. a joint IP policy for research results produced from joint activities. Standardizing procedures might not be feasible.

ITÜ answers

- Having a common policy for the protection of IP rights on research results produced out of EELISA joint actions will be useful or even needed at a certain point, including a co-ownership policy/agreement and distribution of revenues policy.
- Reinforcing connections between specific TTOs experts is also needed, particularly, creating a group or reinforcing connections among expert in IPRs/patents would be good idea.
- Launching a competition focused on early-stage spin-offs and deep-tech start-ups: we had the prototype contest, but it was targeted to consumer goods and services. It might be a good idea having an EELISA competition for identifying research results ready for commercialisation (knowledge mining), but with an industrial or B2B application.
- Having an Innovation Committee, similarly to ACRI (Advisory Council on Research and Innovation) but exclusively focused on innovation.

UPB answers

Develop best practices covering IP management, licensing, spin-offs, and industry collaboration for consistency in tech transfer; Training: Provide capacity-building programs for tech transfer professionals on patent law, negotiation, and commercialization; Tool Adoption: Use common platforms like IP databases and project management tools to streamline processes and encourage collaboration; Regular Evaluation: Implement ongoing reviews to refine tech transfer procedures based on stakeholder feedback.

SNS answers

Create a common approach to training for students in entrepreneurship, and develop shared credentials on this training activity. Organize and participate to hackathon and awards for students and start-ups: they are very good occasion to create a community on innovation, also for VC and SMEs.

4.7.3 Establishing Support Mechanisms

Proposals for establishing support mechanisms at the EELISA level to facilitate technology transfer efforts

UPM answers

- Having a common policy for the protection of IP rights of research results (see above)wp4

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- Having an Innovation Committee, similarly to ACRI (Advisory Council on Research and Innovation) but exclusively focused on innovation.
- Keep boosting connections among DIHs (already started under WP5)

ITÜ answers

- Proposals for establishing support mechanisms at the EELISA level to facilitate technology transfer efforts
- Having a common policy for the protection of IP rights of research results (see above)wp4
- Having an Innovation Committee, similarly to ACRI (Advisory Council on Research and Innovation) but exclusively focused on innovation.
- Keep boosting connections among DIHs (already started under WP5)

ITÜ answers

Centralized Funding: EELISA-level grants for tech transfer, including proof-of-concept and industry partnership funding; Expert Advisory: EELISA-level guidance in legal, business, and market analysis for tech transfer; Networking Events: EELISA-level gatherings connecting researchers, entrepreneurs, industry, and investors; Recognition Programs: EELISA-level awards celebrating successful tech transfer initiatives.

SNS answers

- EELISA-based PoC project for tech transfer;
- EELISA Advisory BOARD on Innovation: it could be a reference point for common initiatives, legal problems on IP management, common guideline approval, etc.
- EELISA Networking: exchange program for personnel of TT offices, academic, researchers, students on innovation activities; organizing common FAIRS, hackathon, awards, communities and events on innovation;
- EELISA stories: best practices and best innovation stories that could inspire all the partners.

4.8 Path towards Entrepreneurial University

4.8.1 Fostering an Entrepreneurial Mindset

Strategies for cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset among students, faculty, and staff

BME answers

In our opinion, to foster an entrepreneurial mindset among students, faculty, and staff, it's essential to integrate subjects related to entrepreneurial education across all faculties. However, this presents challenges, as practical, workshop-style training requires additional instructors and resources, which may not be readily available due to financial constraints (not at BME). Nevertheless, measuring interest through student feedback and enrollment numbers shows that there would be a huge demand for such education.

Additionally, instigating a fundamental change in attitude within the university community is crucial. Lecturers need to transition from viewing research results as merely publication credits to recognizing their potential for long-term market viability. It's worth noting that the investment required to develop both marketable and seemingly "unusable" research results can be comparable. This shift in perspective can encourage researchers to proactively consider market applications during the research topic selection process, fostering a more entrepreneurial approach to academic endeavors.

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ITÜ answers

In each academic semester, ITÜ Genova (Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship) conducts a 5-week accelerated program called JumpStart to foster innovation and entrepreneurial culture across the university. Jumpstart program is a certificate program that includes hands on lectures and workshops that aims at creating awareness about the modern entrepreneurial methodologies including Lean Startup, Business Modeling, design thinking etc. The program also includes asynchronous education modules delivered through a gamified education management platform named MotivaCraft. The program also includes one to one mentoring sessions.

Before the Jumpstart program, an announcement that invites participants who haven't found their co-founders for „Find your Co-founder Event” is made early in the semester across the whole university. Application is open to all students (undergrads and grads) , administrative and academic staff.

UPB answers

Experiential Learning: Provide hands-on opportunities like internships and competitions to foster an entrepreneurial mindset; Risk-Taking Culture: Encourage experimentation and resilience, embracing failure as a chance to learn; Mentorship: Connect aspiring entrepreneurs with successful alumni and industry leaders for guidance; Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Promote cross-disciplinary teamwork to drive innovation and problem-solving.

SNS answers

Create EELISA common training and mentorship programs, for students, faculty and staff.

4.8.2 Integrating Entrepreneurship into the Curriculum

Recommendations for integrating entrepreneurship education into academic programs

BME answers

BME fully supports the integration of entrepreneurship education into academic programs. While acknowledging the current limitations, such as faculty capacity, we recognize the growing demand for such training among students, as evidenced by their feedback. We believe that increasing awareness of intellectual property and fostering innovative thinking requires practical exposure to entrepreneurship, not just theoretical instruction. Therefore, we advocate for the development of specialized courses leveraging online platforms and contemporary technologies to meet the needs of this generation of students.

ITÜ answers

Individuals who successfully complete Jumpstart Entrepreneurship program becomes accredited to take advanced entrepreneurship education modules in 1773 İTU Teknopark Accelerator Program. They also become eligible to get mentorship from qualified mentor pool. The teams can also get consultancy on legal issues and IP issues.

If the duration of the completed modules reaches 30 hours, the students get diploma supplement via İTU Dean of Research.

UPB answers

Entrepreneurship Education: Provide courses covering business essentials for starting and growing ventures; Experiential Learning: Offer hands-on experiences like internships and projects to apply entrepreneurship skills; Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Partner with other disciplines for combined

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entrepreneurship education; Capstone Projects: Facilitate business plan competitions and incubator programs for venture development.

SNS answers

Develop common “light credentials” for innovation training and courses

4.8.3 Supporting Entrepreneurial Ventures

Initiatives to support students and faculty in launching and scaling entrepreneurial ventures

BME answers

BME is enthusiastic about collaborating with a venture capital entity established by the EU aimed at investing in the utilization of intellectual property generated at EELISA universities, whether through startups or spinoffs. We firmly believe that the vast pool of knowledge within the university holds significant market potential with the appropriate support and team in place. To facilitate this, we advocate for the utilization of the online innovation marketplace mentioned earlier, coupled with proactive assistance in establishing industrial partnerships.

ITÜ answers

Both students and academic entrepreneurship is encouraged with Accelerator programs held by 1773 ITÜ Teknopark.

UPB answers

Startup Support: Create incubators and accelerators, offering resources, mentorship, funding, and networking; Financial Assistance: Provide seed funding and grants for venture launch and scaling; Resource Access: Offer co-working spaces, labs, and industry connections; Support Programs: Provide workshops, mentorship, and networking events for entrepreneurs.

SNS answers

ORGANIZE COMMON HACKATON, FAIRS, AWARDS dedicated to innovation for the EELISA partners participation.

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5 Concluding remarks

One of the core achievements of this initiative has been the integration and emphasis on entrepreneurship within the academic curriculum across multiple institutions, fostering an environment where innovative thinking and business acumen are cultivated alongside technical expertise. This approach has been instrumental in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, ensuring that students are not only ready to face the challenges of today's industries but are also equipped to lead and innovate within them.

The collaborative endeavors have also led to the creation of more connected and comprehensive networks, offering students unprecedented access to a pan-European ecosystem of resources, mentorship, and opportunities. This connectivity is pivotal in a world where the boundaries of technology and business are increasingly blurred, and where interdisciplinary and cross-cultural teams are becoming the norm in tackling complex global challenges.

Moreover, the project's focus on sustainable and inclusive practices reflects a deeper understanding of the role that engineers and entrepreneurs must play in shaping the future—not just economically, but socially and environmentally. By instilling the values of sustainability and equity in the learning outcomes, EELISA InnoCORE ensures that the next generation of engineers and entrepreneurs are prepared to make decisions that positively impact the world.

The foundations laid by this project will continue to evolve and adapt, driven by the ongoing collaboration among the EELISA universities and their commitment to excellence and innovation in education. The impacts of these efforts will undoubtedly echo through the successes of its graduates—creative, capable, and socially responsible leaders who will navigate and shape the future of industry and entrepreneurship.

In conclusion, the EELISA InnoCORE project is not just a testament to what can be achieved through cooperation and shared vision among leading educational institutions but also a beacon for future educational endeavors aiming to merge academic excellence with entrepreneurial and industrial innovation. The project's legacy will be defined by the continued success of its students and the sustainable, inclusive growth they drive in the industries and communities they serve.

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6 Appendices

Survey about technology transfer practices of partner institutions and their

6.1 SNS Survey Answers

Re-definition of learning-outcomes for successful industrial and entrepreneurial career (D.6.4.)

WP6 members are kindly asked to fill in the following questionnaire. (If any question requires more detail than the options given in the questionnaire, please write it also in.)

TTO-related Questions

- 1) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available:
SNS Valorization of Research and Technology Transfer: <https://www.sns.it/en/valorisation-research>
- 2) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)
Total staff: 2
1 Economist
0,3 Technicians
0,7 administrative/staff
- 3) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?
 2008
- 4) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures?
50.000 euro
- 5) What is the organizational form of the TTO?
 - a. **As part of the University**
 - b. As an external organization
 - c. Other: _____
- 6) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?
Available services:

Fostering a culture within the institution in technology transfer; providing support for entrepreneurship and intellectual property issues; providing access to a chosen network of

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professionals (legal, financial, and commercial) to facilitate technology transfer and research exploitation to create impact for society

7) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?

- Administrative burden
 - Internal communication difficulties
 - X Lack of resources
 - X For TTO maintenance
 - For patent maintenance
 - To involve external experts
 - X Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
 - X Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
 - Lack of market connections
 - Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
 - Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
- o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

- 1) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023?
3
- 2) How many PCT procedures were initiated?
4
- 3) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed?
2

Trademarks

- 1) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023?
no
- 2) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023?
a. If yes, what was the value? --
no

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 1) How many spinoffs were established at the university **in the past year?**
0 (where spin-off is considered a company in which the University has a share of ownership)
- 2) What are their names
- 3) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
a. _____%
b. No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made

Commercialization Agreements

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- 1) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?
 - a). Yes, using internal resources
 - b). Yes, through an external company
 - c). No**
 - d)

- 2) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?

2
- 3) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?

Medical devices
- 4) What form of compensation was received?
 - **Lump-sum payment**
 - o Average amount: 50.000__ EUR
 - **Royalty**
 - o Amount:
 - Percentage of pre-tax income:%
 - Percentage of revenue: 2-7.%
 - Other:
- 5) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)?

50% of the net income
- 6) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?
 - a. The negotiation was trouble-free
 - b. Other:

Startups

- 1) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?

If start-ups are companies created by professors or other personnel of School, with no shares of the School, there are 4 active start-ups at School

More information <https://www.sns.it/en/spin-and-start-companies-normale>

;
- 2) How much space (m3) is available for university startups?

na
- 3) What kind of support do university startups receive?

Office Space rent; training; participation to events for promotion and matchmaking; network with investors and other
- 4) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

v. point 5

- 5) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)
- 6) Matchmaking event between research and companies together other universities of network JoTTO <https://jotto-fair-2023.b2match.io>
Start Cup Toscana, a business plan competition, organized at regional level
<http://www.startcuptoscana.it/>
Start up competition “Premio nazionale dell’Innovazione” (National Prize of Innovation At national level we participate to the organization of the) <https://www.pnicube.it/pni-2023-premio-nazionale-innovazione>

NEW IDEAS

- 1) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)
 - a. **Yes, it could be very useful to have an external and qualified reference on these topics, because it is hard to have data about the market trends in different industries and these data are needed to define realistic economic values for the fees. Also a legal support, especially with foreign companies, could be useful**
 - b. No, because...
- 2) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies?
no
- 3) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?
Yes, there has been some courses with frontal lessons with teachers, professionals and entrepreneurs of high-tech companies for about 10 students on average. We are planning new initiatives, where there will be more practical cases, more skilled and expert figures and with a deeper interactions between students and who have had an entrepreneurial experience
- 4) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?
We have a couple of co-financed PhDs, that are jointly funded by the school and companies. The IP rights are jointly owned and, in the case of exploitation of the patents, the company has an exclusive license and School receives a compensation
- 7) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?
- 8) They should have a specialistic support in matters related to some topics that had the same experiences in the past (success stories), they should have some kind of incentive in their career if they are involved in technology transfer activities (e.g., additional budget for travels or training; credits for academic career; etc.) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)
multi-disciplinary skills, soft skills along hard skills for entrepreneurship

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Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text) **core courses, industry internship, multi-disciplinary workshops, student startup competitions; challenges**

- 9) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No**
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 10) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No**
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 11) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: we have some consultants on this topic (Free text)
- 12) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No**
 - d. Other: we have external consultants_____ (Free text)
- 13) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No**
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startappers”

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- 1) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why?
 Yes, having a diverse skill-set during the venture building process is essential. In the process of commercializing a scientific innovation, one needs to understand commercial aspects such as the dynamics of the targeted market, the funding strategy, the best suitable go-to-market strategy, the product strategy and the business model. All these Different areas require a complementarity to R&D, diverse skill-set and as a result diverse personalities.
I agree and I suggest also that the founding team should have a mixed composition but first of all there should be strong empathy and trust among its members.
- 2) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?
 I think such generalizations are neither accurate nor useful. There are multiple simple frameworks for personality assessment that are widely used in the academic setting to form high-functioning teams.
- 3) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS? Yes
 Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork? Maybe for startup space rent This could be difficult, but he/she could meet our startupper or start other collaborations with our start-up
- 4) What would be your preferences? Both ok
 - a. - „idea guy/girl“ without a team
 - b. - member looking for a project
 - c. -
- 5) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?
 Yes
- 6) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities? Yes.

6.2 FAU Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

- 8) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available: FAU Consulting Services for Startups: <https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/> / FAU Knowledge and Technology Transfer at FAU: <https://www.fau.de/outreach/fau-fuer-unternehmen-und-organisationen/wissens-und-technologietransfer/> / Patent Management and Inventor Consulting: <https://www.fau.de/outreach/erfindungen-und-patente/erfinden-und-patentieren/>

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- 9) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents) **FAU Consulting Services for Startups: 8 staff members** (<https://www.fau.de/outreach/innovationen-und-gruendungen/gruenden/team/>) / **FAU Knowledge and Technology Transfer at FAU: 4 staff members** (<https://www.fau.de/outreach/erfindungen-und-patente/erfinden-und-patentieren/team/>) / **Patent Management and Inventor Consulting: 4 staff members** (<https://www.fau.de/outreach/erfindungen-und-patente/erfinden-und-patentieren/team/>)
- 10) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?
1982 regarding assistance for joint industry university cooperation
2000 regarding patent management and startup services
- 11) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures? **six-digit range**
- 12) What is the organizational form of the TTO?
 a. As part of the University **As part of the University**
 b. As an external organization
 c. Other: _____
- 13) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues? **Financial and administrative support for industry-university cooperations, Patent management with a high degree of IP coming out of industry-university cooperation, individual startup consulting services and grants / pre seed funding, intense extracurricular entrepreneurship training, life long learning courses for professionals**
- 14) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?
 Administrative burden
 o Internal communication difficulties
 Lack of resources
 For TTO maintenance
 For patent maintenance
 To involve external experts
 o Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
 o Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
 Lack of market connections
 Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
 o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
 o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

- 4) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023?
33 (27 priority applications)
- 5) How many PCT procedures were initiated?
28

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- 6) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed?
26

Trademarks

- 3) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023?
no
- 4) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023? no
a. If yes, what was the value? --

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 4) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year?
3 if only companies with IP-agreements are considered a spinoff,
otherwise 12 (based on knowledge or technology from research)
- 5) What are their names? Mallia Therapeutics GmbH, Amperial Technologies GmbH, Voxray GmbH
- 6) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs? Only licensing agreements
a. _____%
b. No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made

Commercialization Agreements

- 7) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements? Partially, b
a). Yes, using internal resources
b). Yes, through an external company
c). No
d)
- 8) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?
5-10/year
- 9) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover? diverse (e.g. automotive, information technology, medtech, energy and energy storage, biotech ...)
- 10) What form of compensation was received? mixture, huge bandwidth
- Lump-sum payment
o Average amount: _____ EUR
- Royalty
o Amount:
☑ Percentage of pre-tax income:%
☑ Percentage of revenue:%
- Other:
- 11) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)? 30 % to inventors according to legal provisions

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- 12) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?
- The negotiation was trouble-free
 - Other: **Warranties, Indemnification and Liability; conditions**

Startups

- 14) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made? **The question is unclear: There are a lot of startups every year (approx. 20 – 25 per year). We cannot mention them all and their efforts. Or do you mean teams offering support to startups from university?**
- 15) How much space (m³) is available for university startups? **At the university: decentralized space at the institutes (m² varies). At the ZOLLHOF Tech incubator: approx 1.500 – 2.000 m²**
- 16) What kind of support do university startups receive? **Startup Consulting Services, pre seed accelerator programs, pre seed grant programs, workshops for startups, mentoring program**
- 17) What competitions and events have been organised for startups? **Founder's café (networking event), Businessplan Competition Bavaria, pitching events**
- 18) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!) **EELISA Entrepreneurship School, EELISA Next Level: Your Seed and Series A Funding Booster Event, DTA Entrepreneurial Innovation Hub (qualification program with early stage accelerator)**

NEW IDEAS

- 5) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also) **might be interesting**
- Yes, because...
 - No, because...
- 6) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies? **sometimes**
- 7) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?

Digital Tech Academy: 20 students per year (exclusive, 200 applicants per year, business design + prototyping regarding digital innovation)

Founding Business Ideas @FAU (online course): 80 students per year

Impact Creators Program (impact business design): 15 -20 students per year

5 Euro Business Competition (sales competition): 30 – 40 students per year

Innovation Lab (digital prototyping): approx. 30 students per year

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- 8) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case? **Normally industry partner and university conduct a r&d project, University receives money from the industry partner used for costs (materials, machines etc.) and salary for the Ph.D. student will be employed by university. If the employee (=Ph.D. student) makes an invention the university has the respective rights that will be offered to industry partner which has to pay an extra amount for every invention to be transferred (often a lump sum).**
- 19) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career? **Job pool, esp. for startups; team member match making events**
- 20) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text) **innovative and entrepreneurial spirit for entrepreneurial career; sound education for industrial career**
- 21) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text) **entrepreneurship and design thinking courses; university education in STEM**
- 22) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?
- Yes **Yes**
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 23) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?
- Yes **Yes**
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 24) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand**
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 25) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation? **One member in the team of startup consulting services**
- Yes**

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- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

- 26) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products? **A) Yes, partially – this is done in parts by patent management and startup consulting services. But the demand is higher than human resources dedicated for this.**
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startupper“

- 7) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? **Why? Yes, because building up a business needs has a lot of tasks in different fields of expertise – so different qualifications and personalities are necessary and reduce „blind spots“ in business planning**
- 8) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? **Why? I am sure there are traits typical for different scientific disciplines (business, informatics, engineering, humanities); with regard to nationalities / cultural national background within Europe: not sure if existing differences have such a big impact in building startup teams / starting a business**
- 9)
- 10) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS? **Yes, why not?! But the question is: Where does he want to make a scholarship? Should he join entrepreneurship programs or does he want to do an internship at incubators or at startups. – Or all of this? With regard to startups: There is an existing program „ERASMUS for Young Entrepreneurs“ which could be used more often.**
- 11) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork? **Generally yes. Depends on what she/he wants to do and what we can offer.**
- 12) What would be your preferences? **Both is possible**
- a. - „idea guy/girl“ without a team
 - b. - member looking for a project
 - c. -
- 13) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? **Why? Could be interesting if the business idea of the winning team meets a „sweet spot“ in research expertise of the respective host university.**
- 14) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities? **Yes.**

6.3 ITÜ Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

- 15) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available:
TTO webpage: www.1773itutto.com.tr/
- 16) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)
TTO has 7 staff working in university industry cooperation department and financial and administrative department, 3 staff in intellectual property department and 3 board members. In addition to this, we are working with 2 lawyers and 3 different patent agents in our processes.
- 17) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?
Technology transfer office activities at our university started in 2014. It continues with TTO, which started operating within Teknopark in 2023.
- 18) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures? 2013-2023 Total Budget: \$ 1.293.418,25; 2024 Estimated Budget \$ 150.000,00
- 19) What is the organizational form of the TTO?
a. As part of the University
b. As an external organization
c. Other: _____
- 20) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?
- Commercialization of new inventions,
 - Sharing research results,
 - University-industry collaboration,
 - Intellectual property protection and licensing,
 - Entrepreneurship support,
 - Technology transfer management,
 - Increasing awareness.
- 21) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?
- o **Administrative burden**
 - o Internal communication difficulties
 - o Lack of resources
 - For TTO maintenance
 - For patent maintenance
 - To involve external experts
 - o **Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)**
 - o **Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)**
 - o **Lack of market connections**
 - o **Dominance of large companies in business negotiations**
 - o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property

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o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

- 7) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023? **31**
- 8) How many PCT procedures were initiated? **17**
- 9) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed? **3**

Trademarks

- 5) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023? **1**
- 6) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023? **No**
 - a. If yes, what was the value?

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 7) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year?
4
- 8) What are their names?

Spin-Off Name	University's Ownership Stake*
AZO MINERAL TEKNOLOJİLERİ SANAYİ VE TİCARET LTD. ŞTİ.	100%
GAİA MÜHENDİSLİK VE TEKNOLOJİ LTD. ŞTİ.	100%
MTS OKYANUS BİLGİ TEKNOLOJİ SİSTEMLERİ LIMITED ŞİRKETİ	100%
POWELMACH ARGE TEKNOLOJİ MÜHENDİSLİK VE DANIŞMANLIK SAN. VE TİC. LTD. ŞTİ.	100%

*University's Ownership Stake refers to equity stake that the university's academics hold the company

- 9) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
 - a. _____% (given above)
 - b. **No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made**

Commercialization Agreements

- 13) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?

- a). **Yes, using internal resources**
- b). Yes, through an external company
- c). No
- d)

- 14) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?

In total, 17 different technology transfer agreements were signed in 2022 and 2023.

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15) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?

Chemical-Metallurgy, Construction, Environment, Information Technology, Software

16) What form of compensation was received?

- Lump-sum payment
 - o Average amount: 45.000 EURO
- Royalty
 - o Amount:
 - Percentage of pre-tax income:%
 - Percentage of revenue: % 9
- Other:

17) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)?

Inventors: Obtain licensing revenue up to 70%.

18) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?

- a. The negotiation was trouble-free
- b. Other: _____ (Free text, please write about all the difficulties)

Some of the commercialization activities carried out by Istanbul Technical University's Commercialization Unit have not yielded results. The reasons include:

- Increased funding requirements in the commercialization ecosystem,
- Failure to reach a conclusion due to the low levels of prototype development for university patents,
- Changes in product strategies by licensee companies in the market,
- Relatively low quality of patent specifications in the Turkish ecosystem,
- Lack of full engagement by inventors in licensing activities,
- Decrease in resources allocated to Research and Development Activities due to increased exchange rates,
- The relatively new concept of the technology transfer ecosystem in Turkey.

Startups

27) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?

ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park

Within Istanbul Technical University, ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park operates the university incubation center called ITU Cekirdek, which receives thousands of applications each year and supports an average of 500 startups annually. With a track record of supporting over 4700 startups to date, which secured over \$270 million of investment and made over \$200 million of turnover with 10.500 headcount, ITU Cekirdek Incubation Center has been also supporting university startup teams. All these efforts and highlights were globally recognized as it was selected as the top university-business incubator in the world (by UBI Global) and best incubator/accelerator (by Euro

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Asian Startup Awards) in 2023. Some notable examples of these supported ventures from ITU Cekirdek, which has assisted approximately 700+ entrepreneurs from Istanbul Technical University (student/graduate), including the (co-)founders of:

Biolive: Manufactures bioplastic raw materials such in scale-up and next-gen materials such as plant-based leather and also offers sustainable solutions.

- <https://biolivearge.com>
- Valuation: \$30 million,
- Current manufacturing capacity is 800 tons per month.

VSight: Offers the best-in-class B2B SaaS remote collaboration and digital workflow solutions to industrial companies with its all-in-one Augmented Reality Platform dedicated to the mission of empowering the industrial workforce.

- <https://vsight.io/>
- 30+ Countries and 150+ Customers
- Can serve in 12+ Languages and established 20+ Partnerships

Virasoft: Develops artificial intelligence (AI) and digital pathology solutions for cancer diagnosis and research.

- <https://www.virasoft.com>
- Its solutions reach 140,000 cases yearly in over 20 institutions
- Total investment exceeding \$5 million & forged a strategic partnership with laboratories at Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Vivoo: Develops at-home urine test & mobile application that helps users boost their wellness to make body data more accessible and understandable for all consumers worldwide, empowering them to live better lives.

- <https://vivoo.io>
- Raised over \$18 million in total funding,
- Partnering with 150 distributors, it reached over 100,000 app users across more than 120 countries.

ITU GINOVA

Each semester ITU GINOVA organizes an education program for teams builded up by ITU students. After the end of the program, students present their business ideas and after jury voting 3 teams are choosen as first three teams. ITU GINOVA supports these teams by providing some perks, networking events with investors and giving mentorship. One of these group, namely "BUMU Dijital" already realised their business idea and founded their company.

28) How much space (m3) is available for university startups?

ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park has an area of 130,000m2, and although none of these areas are dedicated exclusively to university startups, they can all be technically used by them. To do this,

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they need to meet the necessary application process and criteria. Additionally, as ITU Cekirdek Incubation Center, our main value proposition and differentiator are our acceleration programs that enable the growth and scaling of our startups. Therefore, although having an office is not a strict requirement, our programs are designed to be suitable for online participation to accommodate the dynamics of the era and to be founder-friendly. It's also worth noting that all ten buildings of ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park offer more commonly preferred co-working and rentable spaces for startups.

At ITU GINOVA we have a co-working space around 30 m².

29) What kind of support do university startups receive?

ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park;

- One-on-one meetings with 500+ mentors,
- Utilization of ITU Çekirdek Office at ITU Maslak campus 24/7,
- Advantageous discounts or completely free use of 50+ products and services such as AWS, Google Cloud, MathWorks, Iyzico, Hubspot, etc.,
- Meeting with 40+ investors and chasing the opportunity of securing investments,
- Access to laboratories and prototyping workshops,
- Expansion to global markets with our international acceleration program,
- Benefit from patent support with consultancy from ARI Technology Transfer Office,
- PR & promotional services tailored to startup,
- Access to national and international fair participation support,
- Utilization of state incentives (i.e., tax advantages) within the scope of ITU ARI Teknokent Technology Development Zone,
- Access to PR opportunities for domestic and foreign stakeholders at Big Bang, the most important startup competition in the entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Supports provided by ITU GINOVA;

- Education programs
- Workshops
- Mentorship
- Inspirational talks
- Networking events with investors

30) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

ITU ARI Teknokent Science Park

Throughout the year, startups can participate in 30+ investor or stakeholder demo days per year if deemed suitable, attend networking events held twice a month, and be invited to Game Changers Talks event series where we organize around 5 to 10 talks a year, inviting key figures from the Turkish entrepreneurship ecosystem as speakers. Additionally, we organize the largest event of the Turkish Entrepreneurship Ecosystem, the Big Bang Startup Challenge, every December, where we showcase the most successful startups applying to our incubation center on the live stage. In fact, last year our Big Bang Startup Challenge live event hosted 4000+ attendees in two days, reached 6 million social media users through channels and more than \$50 million investments, awards and grants in total were declared as they were received throughout the year by our startups in 2023.

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31) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

ITU Cekirdek values sharing and ecosystem development, therefore it both shares its know-how on this matter and follows a strategy open to collaboration with institutions that will contribute to its own development. In Turkey, we partner up with the Duzce University and its science park for the government-supported BIGG program which allows pre-seed investment to R&D-based startups. We also support the high-potential startups of our partner university science parks through accepting the ones they recommend that fulfill our criteria to our pre-incubation program. Apart from that, we actively participate with our entrepreneurs in startup events organized by other universities in Turkey, and we also invite them to our relevant events.

Additionally, since we aim to further globalize, we currently focus on European Union projects. We also collaborate with Drexel University (US), to make our biotechnology startups to benefit from their know-how and network. Finally, collaboration efforts are currently ongoing with Sophia Antipolis (France) which is supported by various universities and organizations.

Events have been organized by **ITU GINOVA**;

- Jump Start Entrepreneurship Program
- Town hall meetings
- Find your co-founder event

NEW IDEAS-

9) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)

a. Yes, because...

b. **No, because we don't have expert on this topic at ITU GINOVA.**

10) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies? YES

11) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?

- Each semester, counselling course provide to the students and within the scope of this course, students are informed about entrepreneurship.
- Jump Start entrepreneurship program organizes each semester, after collecting the applications, 50 students are selected as participators of the program. The program takes 4 weeks.

12) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?

The intellectual property belongs to the doctoral student's university or to the university and the company in proportion to their rights.

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32) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?

Doctoral students can be provided with entrepreneurship and technology transfer support. In this context, resources and consultancy services can be offered to commercialize their research and facilitate technology transfer. Additionally, they can receive mentorship from industry professionals or alumni. Moreover, they can find opportunities to work on real-world problems through programs and projects enabling collaboration with the industry.

33) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)

- **Leadership:** Team management, motivation.
- **Communication:** Effective written, verbal communication.
- **Problem Solving:** Identification, analysis, solution.
- **Creativity:** Innovative thinking, idea generation
- **Strategy:** Goal setting, planning, resource management.
- **Finance:** Basic knowledge, budgeting, cash flow.
- **Flexibility:** Adaptation to change, rapid adaptation.

34) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)
Istanbul Technical University is at the forefront among institutions providing support to entrepreneurs and students in the fields of leadership, communication, problem-solving, creativity, strategy, finance, and flexibility in Turkey.

In addition to the conventional formats such as course and certificate program, new learning formats such as learning station can be applied to the students. Learning stations can provide students a more flexible education program.

35) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?

- a. Yes
- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

36) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?

- a. Yes
- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

37) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?

- a. Yes

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- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

38) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?

- a. Yes
- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

39) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?

- a. Yes
- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startupper“

- 15) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why?
- 16) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?
- 17) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS?
- 18) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork?
- 19) What would be your preferences?
 - a. - „idea guy/girl“ without a team
 - b. - member looking for a project
 - c. -
- 20) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?
- 21) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

6.4 UPB Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

- 22) Please share the webpages of the [University Technology Transfer Office \(TTO\)](https://upb.ro/ghid-valorificare-rezultate-cdi/ghid-valorificare/siit/) <https://upb.ro/ghid-valorificare-rezultate-cdi/ghid-valorificare/siit/> , Startup support Team (STS) <https://antreprenoriat.upb.ro/> /Innovation Unit (IU) if available:

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- 23) How many staff members does TTO (2) /STS (4)/ IU have, and what is their composition?
TTO (2) /STS (4)
 Bussiness development, administrative staff, legal, economists, professors (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)
- 24) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?
TTO (10 y), STS (7 y)
- 25) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures?
 N/A
- 26) What is the organizational form of the TTO?
 a. As part of the University
 b. As an external organization
 c. Other: _____
- 27) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?
Helping professors to patent
- 28) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?
 o Administrative burden
o Internal communication difficulties
 o Lack of resources
 For TTO maintenance
 For patent maintenance
 To involve external experts
o Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
o Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
 o Lack of market connections
 o Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
 o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
 o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023? - 29

- 10) How many PCT procedures were initiated? - none
 11) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed? - none

Trademarks

- 7) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023? - no
 8) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023? - no
 a. If yes, what was the value?

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 10)** How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year? **4**
 11) What are their names?
Future Instal Group SRL

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Galaxy Studio Events

Global Foto SRL

PLUMBING SQUAD S.R.L.

- 12) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
- _____%
 - No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made

Commercialization Agreements

- 19) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?
- Yes, using internal resources
 - Yes, through an external company
 - No
 -
- 20) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?
- none
- 21) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover? - N/A
- 22) What form of compensation was received? - N/A
- Lump-sum payment
 - o Average amount: _____ EUR
 - Royalty
 - o Amount:
 - Percentage of pre-tax income:%
 - Percentage of revenue:%
 - Other:
- 23) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)? - N/A
- 24) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason? - N/A
- The negotiation was trouble-free
 - Other: _____ (Free text, please write about all the difficulties)

Startups

- 40) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?
- Recycluxx – startup company that finds litter in oceans. They raised 90k euros so far
- SmartRDI – participated in several Horizon projects, generally in the area of agrifood
- 41) How much space (m³) is available for university startups?
- N/A
- 42) What kind of support do university startups receive?
- Mentoring, connections, infrastructure
- 43) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

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Innovation Labs (<https://www.innovationlabs.ro>)

Fii antreprenor (<https://upb.ro/fii-antreprenor-5-0/>)

44) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

We did a hackathon together with EELISA unfolds partners

Innovation Labs is in collaboration with 17 RO universities

NEW IDEAS

13) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)

a. Yes, because we need know-how from other that are doing this more frequently

b. No, because...

14) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies?

YES

15) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?

There are annual trainings on entrepreneurship, as well as several master's courses that cover some entrepreneurship topics.

16) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?

In RO the PhD is only public PhD, we don't have industrial PhD.

45) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?

Matchmaking events, training and awareness on IPR, incentives for commercialization vs articles

46) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)

Strong tech skills, strong leadership and management

47) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)

Technical skills

48) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?

a. Yes

b. No, but there is a demand

c. No

d. Other: _____ (Free text)

49) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?

a. Yes

b. No, but there is a demand

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- c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 50) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
- a. Yes
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 51) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?
- a. Yes
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 52) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?
- a. Yes
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startappers”

- 22) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why?
- Yes, startup teams should be of mixed composition from an education point of view (engineering and economist) but also from a personality point of view, so that they can have multiple perspectives on the problem they are solving.
- 23) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?
- I think that best students are the same all over Europe. There are countries where, by culture, some students are more failure resistant.
- 24) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS?
- Yes
- 25) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork?
- Yes
- 26) What would be your preferences?
- a. - „idea guy/girl” without a team

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b. - member looking for a project

c. -

27) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?

Yes, a 1-year post-doctoral fellowship for startup development on top of the PhD idea, so that the PhD ideas with commercial potential are valorized.

28) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

Yes.

6.5 ENPC Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

29) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available: <https://ecoledespons.fr/co-innovation-lab>

30) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)

(1 part-time for legal issues, 1 part-time responsible for valorisation; (IU) 2 person in full-time , 3 engineers; (STS), 1 full-time)

31) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation? 2017

32) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures? 80.000 Euros

33) What is the organizational form of the TTO?

- a. As part of the University
- b. As an external organization
- c. Other: _____

34) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?

Knowledge of nationale ecosyteme.

35) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?

- Administrative burden
- Internal communication difficulties
- Lack of resources accompagnement transformaton
- For TTO maintenance
- For patent maintenance
- To involve external experts
- Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
- Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
- Lack of market connections
- Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
- Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property

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o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

- 12) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023? **0**
 13) How many PCT procedures were initiated? **8**
 14) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed? **1 USA**

Trademarks

- 9) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023? **0**
 10) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023? **0**
 a. If yes, what was the value?

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 13) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year? **0**
 14) What are their names?
 15) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
 a. _____%
 b. No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made

Commercialization Agreements

- 25) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?
 a). **Yes, using internal resources**
 b). Yes, through an external company
 c). No
 d)
- 26) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?
6
- 27) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?

Construction

- 28) What form of compensation was received?
 - Lump-sum payment
 o Average amount: _____ EUR
 - **Royalty**
 o Amount:
 Percentage of pre-tax income:%
 Percentage of revenue:%
 - Other:

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29) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)? **None**

30) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason? **NO**

- a. The negotiation was trouble-free
- b. Other: _____ (Free text, please write about all the difficulties)

Startups

53) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?

Startups created by students within the past year:

- Wander : geolocalized entertainment application
- T-start : provides personalized t-shirts/goodies for events
- Mona cours : innovative private tutoring platform
- Capella : AI to help parents to manage baby cries
- Izyleaf : web platform for used car sales
- R-Everlands Initiatives : design and construction of sustainable refuge cities

54) How much space (m3) is available for university startups?

One coworking room, about 30 m²

One incubator ran by Alumni association in Station F 150m²

Partnership with a local public incubator Descartes Development & Innovation.

55) What kind of support do university startups receive?

Pepite via National Student Entrepreneur Status:

- **Pepite organization** (students hub for innovation, transfer and entrepreneurship) aims at **raising awareness of entrepreneurship to every student** – [pole étudiant pour l’innovation, le transfert et l’entrepreneuriat]
- Getting this status allows the students to **get some coaching, network and training for projects in early stage** ;
- They have access to **contests and prizes**.

Courses to entrepreneurship : Creation of innovative Enterprises, Design thinking, Intellectual Property

Funding – scholarship via Fondation des Ponts

56) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

Nucleation – ideation Event = Hackathon One night to innovate: ones a year in december

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57) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

One night to innovate (Une Nuit pour Entreprendre) involves Universities from all the Paris Region, and EELISA members are welcome as well.

NEW IDEAS

17) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)

a. Yes, because...

b. No, national markets are very conservative

18) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies?

Yes (aggressive is a big word but their is the idea)

19) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?

Yes, the statut of 'eleve entrepreneur' entrepreneurial students, gives oppurtunity to training and support, app. 6 students for year

Courses

20) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?

It depends in each agreement.

58) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?

Competitive salary,

59) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)

Now how to take risk, networking and 'feel the chance'

60) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)

Risk management courses and networking oppurtunities

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- 61) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?
- a. Yes, with external partners
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 62) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?
- a. Yes, via external partner Station F
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No,
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 63) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 64) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 65) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?
- a. Yes
 - b. No, but there is a demand
 - c. No
 - d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startappers”

- 29) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why?

Yes, in order to address the multiple aspects of entrepreneurship: communication, business, accounting, law, R & D...

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30) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?

No, not within European Union

31) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS?

Yes, a scholarship to support project during one year

32) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork?

Yes

33) What would be your preferences?

- a. - „idea guy/girl“ without a team
- b. - member looking for a project
- c. -

34) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?

The winning team could be hosted and benefit to programs in several incubators among the alliance.

35) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

Why not, in cooperation with other members.

6.6 SSSA Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

- 36) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available: <https://www.santannapisa.it/en/outreach-impact/knowledge-transfer>
- 37) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents) **7 staff members (lawyers, engigneer, admistrators)**
- 38) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation? **2005**
- 39) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures? **50.000,00 €**
- 40) What is the organizational form of the TTO?
a. As part of the University
 b. As an external organization
 c. Other: _____
- 41) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?

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The Technology Transfer Office (TTO) collaborates with researchers for the exploitation of research results. The office promotes the industrial application of research results and products and helps the researcher protect their IP

42) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?

- o Administrative burden
- o Internal communication difficulties
- o Lack of resources
 - For TTO maintenance
 - For patent maintenance
 - To involve external experts
- o Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
- o Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
- o Lack of market connections
- o Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
- o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
- o Other:

The intellectual property management in PNRR projects poses a significant challenge for our office.

Patents

- 15) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023? **9**
- 16)** How many PCT procedures were initiated? **9**
- 17) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed? **10**

Trademarks

- 11) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023? **NO**
- 12) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023? **NO**
- a. If yes, what was the value?

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 16) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year? **5**
accredited spin-offs related to 4 established start-ups and 1 in the process of being established
- 17) What are their names? **MyEcho Srl -**
SoundSafe Care Srl - AIVESP Srl - Celeste Srl
- 18) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
 a. 0 %
 b. **No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made**

Commercialization Agreements

- 31) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?
 a) **Yes, using internal resources**
 b) Yes, through an external company

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- c) No
d)
- 32) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?
6 technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners
- 33) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?
Mainly Life science industry
- 34) What form of compensation was received?
- **Lump-sum payment**
 - o Average amount: _____ EUR
 - **Royalty**
 - o Amount:
 - Percentage of pre-tax income:%
 - Percentage of revenue:%
 - Other:
- 35) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)?
50%
- 36) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?
- a. The negotiation was trouble-free
 - b. Other:
 - Discussion related to the content of the agreement(warranties;milestones)**

Startups

- 66) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?
**The university has within it 42 Start Up recognized as Spin-Offs, operating mainly in the Automation and Robotics sector (29.7 percent of the total), Biomedical (to be understood in a broad sense, as the production of medical devices including robotic ones, for 18.9 percent), ICT and electronics (where 21.6 percent of the enterprises are present) and the Innovation Services sector (21.6 percent of the total). Also prominent remains the Agritech sector (8.1 percent of enterprises in the total).
The sector where enterprises with the highest value of turnover and employees are found in ICT and electronics, the latter of which has a corporate structure involving third party companies.**
- 67) How much space (m3) is available for university startups?
There is no space reserved for university start-ups, but space and access to university laboratories can be requested within agreements signed between the university and start-ups.
- 68) What kind of support do university startups receive?
The University promotes meetings with investors and competitions to access funding for business idea development. It also promotes the continuation of collaboration with the School's research groups within EU, National, and Regional projects.

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Finally, it seeks to foster collaboration among the University's startups within the so-called "Spin-Off Club", where companies can get to know each other by seeking ways to establish business collaborations such as joint product development or supply relationships.

69) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

NA

70) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

- **Start Cup Toscana: a regional start up competition organised together with all Tuscan universities and the Technology Transfer Office of the Tuscan region**
- **Contamination Lab for PhDs and CyB+ organised by the University of Pisa**

NEW IDEAS

21) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)

a. Yes, because...

b. No, because... **our university has a policy for this activity**

22) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies?

NO

23) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?

Within the School, the HTE (High-tech Entrepreneurship) Course is organized annually and is aimed at PhD and MSc students from different disciplines of study such as STEM, Social Science and Humanities. Young researchers and post-docs interested in high-tech entrepreneurship are also eligible.

The course is structured over 20 hours and cuts across the various issues that need to be addressed to realize a Business Project such as patent exploitation, university-industry collaborations, contract research, starting a new business, commercialization of high-tech inventions, etc. The goal is to lead participants to have a business model and business plan ready by the end of the course.

The average number of students participating in the course is about 30.

24) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?

The office usually tries to negotiate an initial co-ownership of industrial property rights generated by the PhD providing for a TT transfer agreement after the publication of the patent.

71) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?

They could be both enhanced and supported economically and financially as well:

- **Entrepreneurial training**
- **Scouting foreign markets**
- **State and private incentives for opening start-ups**
- **Free mentoring by professionals in the relevant industry**
- **De-fiscalisation of salaries for the first 5 years of activity**
- **Space and laboratories for free use for the first two years of activity by incubators or**

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with financial return from the third year of the start-up's life by the host facility

72) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)

To be successful:

- **You need to be very good at cultivating relationships with all stakeholders in the area of interest**
- **Have emotional intelligence for managing the working team**
- **Have adequate and interdisciplinary training distributed among the members of the startup team**
- **Continue to make Innovation both in products and processes, as well as in ways of reaching the customer in line with new technologies and communication management**
- **Always compare themselves with different realities both in their home country and in other countries to enrich their training in the field**
- **Have a win-to-win approach with their suppliers**

73) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)

These skills can be acquired through numerous training opportunities, pitch competitions, and special courses.

74) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?

- Yes
- No, but there is a demand
- No**
- Other: _____ (Free text)

75) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?

- Yes
- No, but there is a demand
- No**
- Other: _____ (Free text)

76) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?

- Yes
- No, but there is a demand
- No**
- Other: _____ (Free text)

77) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?

- Yes
- No, but there is a demand
- No**

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d. Other: _____ (Free text)

78) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?

- a. Yes
- b. No, but there is a demand
- c. No**
- d. Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startupper”

36) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why? **Yes, a mixed composition is an added value.**

37) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?

This question is not in line with the ethical policy of the Scuola

38) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS? **Yes**

Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork?

The Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna will evaluate each initiative proposed by the network

39) What would be your preferences?

- a. - „idea guy/girl” without a team
- b. - member looking for a project
- c. -

NA

40) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?

The Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna will evaluate each initiative proposed by the network

41) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

The Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna will evaluate each initiative proposed by the network

6.7 UPM Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

Overview – UPM (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

UPM TTO is made of two units: the Centre for Support for Technological Innovation (CAIT, by its Spanish acronym) and the Office for Research Results Transfer Activities (OTRI, by its Spanish acronym). Together, these two units constitute UPM Technology Transfer Office (OTC by its Spanish acronym, *Oficina de Tránsferencia de Conocimiento*).

- **Office for Research Results Transfer Activities (OTRI by its Spanish acronym)**

<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/OTRI>

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OTRI stands for *Oficina de Transferencia de Resultados de Investigación* (Office for Research Results Transfer Activities). The OTRI develops the following activities: Protection of research results; identification and dissemination of the University Technological Offer; counselling and management of University-Company/Industry research project proposals; commercialization of technologies; creation of technology-based companies; popularization of scientific and technological research results generated in UPM; technological Surveillance for companies and institutions from the Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) sector. UPM TTO is made of the following units:

- Unit “Intellectual and Industrial Property”
- Unit “Commercialization of R&D results” (commercialisation agreements, patents)
- Unit “Scientific Culture”
- Unit “University-Industry Chairs”
- Unit “Public-Private Partnerships”, including industrial doctorates
- OTRI Network-Indicators

- **Centre for Support for Technological Innovation (CAIT by its Spanish acronym)**

<https://montegancedo.upm.es/Transferencia/CAIT>

CAIT stands for *Centro de Apoyo a la Innovación Tecnológica* (Centre for the Support of Technological Innovation). The aim of CAIT UPM is to help detecting high potential ideas, technologies and entrepreneurs, educating UPM community in innovation and entrepreneurship and creating high growth potential companies at UPM's community. Therefore, it develops its work around four specific parameters that define the birth of the project: team building, scientific and technological knowledge, supporting resources, and business model. In order to achieve these goals, CAIT offers the following:

- Advice and assistance.
- Monitoring of the project from the very first step.
- Analysis of the project feasibility.
- Training activities targeted to the needs of the team.
- Visibility for investors.
- Support in seeking funding.
- Business Plan Competition actúaupm.
- UPM2T programme

43) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available:

- ✓ General webpage on innovation: <https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion>
- ✓ OTRI: <https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/OTRI>
- ✓ Centre for Support for Technological Innovation: <https://montegancedo.upm.es/Transferencia/CAIT>

Additionally, it is worth noting the following webpages:

- ✓ Digital Innovation Hub. The Digital Innovation Hub is an online marketplace compiling UPM's technological offer (infrastructures, equipment, technological services).
<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/>
- ✓ Entrepreneurship and start-up services:
<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/CreacionEmpresas>
- ✓ UPM Thematic Knowledge Communities:
<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/Comunidades>
- ✓ Digital Innovation Hub AIR4S: <https://www.air4s.eu/>

44) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)

OTRI	Eight (8) people + the Director
------	---------------------------------

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Director: Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa • Two lawyers • One economist • One master degree in physics • One PhD in physics • Two journalists
CAIT	<p>Seven (7) people + the Director</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Director: Claudio Feijóo • Five innovation and tech transfer experts (two of them are telecommunication engineers). • Two communication experts. • One administrative assistant.

45) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?

OTRI	<p>The OTRI was created in 1989 and, since 1996, it is registered in the national register of Offices for Research Results Transfer Activities (RedOTRI):</p> <p>http://www.redotriuniversidades.net/index.php/presentacion?id=272)</p>
CAIT	<p>The CAIT was created in 2010.</p>

46) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures?

- Patents: 75,000 per year
- UPM2T and actúaupm programmes: 75,000 euros per year
- Membership in associations (membership fee): 120,000 per year
- Travel costs: 18,000 euros per year
- Business analyses tools: 15,000 euros per year
- (To this we need to add all salaries)

47) What is the organizational form of the TTO?

- a. **As part of the University. Both the CAIT and the OTRI are constituent parts of UPM.**
- ~~b. As an external organization~~
- ~~c. Other: _____~~

48) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?

- High specialization of the teams
- Teams and services well-known by the academic community
- Use of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- Participation in national and international tech transfer events and fora
- Well established methods for all processes

49) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?

- o **Administrative burden**
- o Internal communication difficulties
- o Lack of resources
 - For TTO maintenance
 - For patent maintenance
 - To involve external experts

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- o Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
- o Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
- o Lack of market connections
- o Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
- o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
- o Other: _____

Heavy workload of the teams

Patents

18) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023?

In 2023, there were 33 patent applications.

In the last five years, the number of yearly patent applications ranged between 46 and 33, with between 27 to 38 patent granted per year. It is also worth considering software registrations. In 2023, there 24 applications for software registration.

Patent applications in the last five years at UPM:

Patents granted in the last five years:

Applications of software registration

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19) How many PCT procedures were initiated?

20) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed?

In 2023, there were a total of 17 international extensions filed, out of which 7 PCT and 2 USA extensions.

International extensions filed in the last five years at UPM, including PCT and USA extensions:

Trademarks

13) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023?

No. All UPM trademarks are institutional trademarks (e.g. emblems of engineering schools)

14) ~~Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023?~~

~~—a. If yes, what was the value?~~

Commercialization Agreements

37) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?

Both a) and b).

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- a). Yes, using internal resources
- b). Yes, through an external company

c). No

d) As explained above, the OTRI has a unit for the “Commercialization of R&D results” (licencing agreements, patents). This unit supports and advices researchers in all that has to do with the commercialization of R&D results, including advice for the negotiation and drafting of agreements and the financial management of licence contracts.

a. How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?

In 2023, UPM entered into a total of 6 licence contracts, out of which 5 with external companies and one with a UPM spin-off. By the end of 2023, there were also 13 additional contracts under negotiation. Licence contracts entered into in the last years:

38) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?

- Agriculture, Forestry, Natural Resources, Land Use and Blue Growth
- Architecture, Baukultur and Creativity
- Bioeconomy, Biotechnology and Food Systems
- Science for Engineering and Architecture
- Climate, Energy and Mobility
- Space and Earth Observation
- Industry. Materials and Circular Economy
- Social Innovation, Open Science, Governance and Education Science
- Health and Wellbeing
- Security, Defence and Disaster-Resilience
- Inclusive Society, gender, Diversity
- Digital Technologies, Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, 5G, Robotics

39) What form of compensation was received? It depends

- Lump-sum payment when a patent is sold. The average amount a patent sells for is 300,000 euros.
- Royalty. Royalties usually have a fixed fee between 1,500 euros and 6,000 euros —the set amount depends on sales and on other factors such as the link with UPM (e.g. a UPM spinoff)— plus a variable

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percentage between 3% and 6%, depending on sales. UPM spinoffs can have up to 4 years of deferment period.

40) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)?

50% goes to the researcher himself/herself and 35% goes to the researcher’s research group/s.

41) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?

Usually the negotiation is trouble-free. The most intense debates lie on the following aspects:

- Percentage of royalties and the base (if the royalty percentage is calculated on the gross or net sales, etc.).
- When the contract includes a pre-emption right for the purchase of the patent.
- Termination terms (if the company is not selling enough or does not reach a certain turnover).

Spinoffs / Spinouts and start-ups: overview

UPM has one programme specifically targeting start-ups (actúaupm) and another one (UPM2T) targeting more specifically researchers with mature enough technologies to become spin-offs. In 2023, 6 start-ups and/or spin-offs were created. Below you will find a graph showing the number of start-ups and/or spin-offs created in the last years.

Spinoffs / Spinouts

The main programme supporting spin-offs at UPM is UPM2T. UPM2T is a 10-weeks online programme that aims to support researchers and high-tech entrepreneurs on their way to validate a successful business based on technology.

<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/innovacion/CreacionEmpresas/Servicios/UPM2T>

actúaupm (Business Idea Competition and actúaupm stage 4) are also open and targeted to spin-offs. See a more detailed description below.

19) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year? See above.

20) What are their names? This information is not available.

21) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?

a. 0% for the time being, but UPM is working on an internal procedure to regulate this.

b. No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made

Startups

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79) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?

At UPM, there is the entrepreneurship group UPM, which is made up of individuals from different centres within UPM. The group is engaged in:

1. Community engagement
2. Idea generation
3. Business planning

Additionally, there is the actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts. actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts is a community of individuals who come together to support the growth and development of innovative new businesses. This network is typically composed of investors, who provide funding and financial support to startups, and experts, who offer mentorship guidance, and industry-specific knowledge to help entrepreneurs succeed.

The main mission of the whole CAIT team is to support startups.

80) How much space (m3) is available for university startups?

The business centre (*centro de empresas*) offers space and facilities to host companies in three different locations: Montegancedo Campus, Campus Sur and TecnoGetafe. Currently, there are 15 companies located and operating in the business centres. There are 3,500 square meters available for startups to setup their offices plus 7,813 square meters of common spaces (canteen and others).

81) What kind of support do university startups receive?

82) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?

actúaupm (UPM Entrepreneurship Program) is the main programme in UPM for start-ups and entrepreneurs. Its main objective is the generation of innovative companies with high growth potential and supporting the entrepreneurial spirit. It develops its work around four pillars: the business idea, the team, the resources that support the project, and the business model that the three previous concepts give rise to. actúaupm program services are: Follow-up from the initial phase to the establishment of the company; analysis of the feasibility of the project; ongoing advice; guidance in the writing of the business plan; training actions geared to the needs of the team; visibility for investors and support in the search for financing; and the actúaupm Business Idea Competition with already twenty editions held.

actúaupm consists of various stages covering the different phases of a start-up. It is worth noting:

- **actúaupm business model competition**, which is open to EELISA: <https://eelisa.eu/events/join-the-third-phase-of-actua-upms-start-up-contest-now-open-for-eelisa-members/>
- **actúaupm stage 4 (fase 4)**, for more mature ideas. Startups receive mentorship, coaching, and access to resources such as funding, office space, and networking opportunities. The goal of this phase is to help startups refine their business models, identify target markets, and develop a scalable growth strategy.

Annual event WIT (Technology Innovation Workshops).

83) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

EELISA InnoCORE and, previously, EELISA Unfolds has put in place a whole array of joint activities: <https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/> and <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-unfolds-2/>

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NEW IDEAS

- 25) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)
- a. In the future, the theoretic idea is that EELISA evolves, and extends or creates new services covering the whole consortium. Similar to the individual HEIs, EELISA could have an expert team on commercialisation supporting the whole alliance.
- 26) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies? UPM has strong links and a long-lasting tradition of working with companies. In general terms, there are no mayor troubles when negotiating with companies.
- 27) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate? Yes, many. In addition to actúaupm (see above), UPM participates in different KICs (Knowledge Innovation Communities) of the EIT (European Institute of Innovation and Technology): EIT Digital, EIT Health, EIT Raw Materials, Climate KIC and Urban Mobility. It is worth recalling that innovation and entrepreneurship are key areas of action of KICs.
<https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/iniciativas/eit?id=4df7c128c4133710VgnVCM10000009c7648a&fmt=detail&prefmt=articulo>

Additionally, **many degrees both at undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate level include training on entrepreneurship and innovation.**

- 28) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?
UPM sent a detailed document about how industrial PhD programmes work at UPM in 2022. Please check the document. Attached again.
- 29) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?
We do not understand this question
- 30) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)
 Having a successful entrepreneurial career requires both technical knowledge as well as cross-cutting skills and knowledge.

Technical	Deep technical knowledge
	Experience in applying technical knowledge to reality
Cross-cutting skills and knowledge objectively assessed/measured	Skills (communication, creativity, capacity to face complex problems)
	Knowledge (economics, financial Knowledge, human resources, project management)

- 31) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)
 Project-based learning
 Internships in companies and also in university departments
 International exchanges
- 32) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?

a. Yes

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- b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 33) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?
a. Yes
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 34) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
a. Yes
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ UPM has courses on product development and project management in many degrees both at undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate level
- 35) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?
a. Yes. Any of the CAIT members mentioned above as well as the director of the OTRI (Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa) or the European and International Project Office (Roberto Martínez, Ana Belén Bermejo), any of these UPM team members offer support in team-building and mediation.
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)
- 36) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?
a. Yes See above (CAIT and OTRI)
b. No, but there is a demand
c. No
d. Other: _____ (Free text)

“ERASMUS for Startupers”

- 42) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why? Obviously. Setting up a company / launching a startup requires many different skills and types of knowledge, it is not just about the technical knowledge (“being the best engineer is not enough”) but other skills and other types of knowledge are necessary (business development, commercialisation, human resources, etc.). This is why having a mixed composition of startup teams is not only important but fundamental.
- 43) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why? Sometimes stereotypes are partially true. There is a stereotype about Spanish engineers that we think it is true, that is that Spanish engineers are able to face unknown situations where there are no established procedures yet.
- 44) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS? A whole year might be too long. A short course, micro-credentials, something shorter sounds more adequate.
- 45) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork? EELISA institutions are already welcoming foreign startuppers, particularly from other EELISA institutions. This is already done under EELISA. Under EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds,

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EELISA partners have opened many of their start-up programmes, services and teams to all EELISA partners. For instance, actúaupm business idea competition is open to all EELISA partners.

46) What would be your preferences?

- a. „idea guy/girl” without a team
- b. member looking for a project
- c.

47) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why? Idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration.

48) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

For questions 4), 6) and 7), please take into account that this is already done under EELISA. Under EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds, EELISA has put in place joint initiatives, training and competitions. Moreover, EELISA partners have opened many of their start-up programmes, services and teams to all EELISA partners. More information here: <https://eelisa.eu/innovation-entrepreneurship/>

6.8 BME Survey Answers

TTO-related Questions

50) Please share the webpages of the University Technology Transfer Office (TTO), Startup support Team (STS)/Innovation Unit (IU) if available:

www.innovacio.bme.hu

51) How many staff members does TTO /STS/IU have, and what is their composition? (e.g., lawyers, economists, administrators, patent agents)

4 person (2 lawyers, 2 economists)

52) Since when has TTO/STS/IU been in operation?

2019

53) What is the available budget for TTO/STS/IU for initiating and maintaining intellectual property procedures?

75.000 EUR

54) What is the organizational form of the TTO?

- a. As part of the University
- b. As an external organization
- c. Other: _____

55) What are considered the TTO's greatest virtues?

- market experience,
- broad perspective,
- pricing experience,

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- experience in industrial property protection
- 56) What are considered the TTO's greatest challenges?
- o Administrative burden
 - o Internal communication difficulties
 - o Lack of resources
 - ☑ For TTO maintenance
 - ☑ For patent maintenance
 - ☑ To involve external experts
 - o Researcher attitude (prioritizing publication over commercialization)
 - o Lack of entrepreneurial skills (either within the team or among colleagues)
 - o Lack of market connections
 - o Dominance of large companies in business negotiations
 - o Difficulty in elevating the university's intellectual property
 - o Other: _____ (Free text)

Patents

- 21) How many new domestic (own country) patent applications were filed in 2023?
- 5
- 22) How many PCT procedures were initiated?
- 2
- 23) How many EU/USA applications/extensions were filed?
- 2

Trademarks

- 15) Were there any new trademark applications in 2023?
- yes, 5
- 16) Were there any trademark utilization agreements in 2023?
- a. If yes, what was the value?
- 375 EUR

Spinoffs / Spinouts

- 22) How many spinoffs were established at the university in the past year?
- 4
- 23) What are their names?
- iMotionDrive, DrivebyCloud, LabShare, aHead
- 24) What is the university's ownership stake in these spinoffs?
- a. 10% (in 2 companies)
- b. No ownership stake, but a licensing agreement was made (in 2 companies)

Commercialization Agreements

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- 42) Does the university conduct market research before entering into commercialization agreements?
- Yes, using internal resources
 - Yes, through an external company
 - No
 -
- 43) How many technology transfer agreements were made with industrial partners in recent years?
3 (from this 2 with the spinoffs)
- 44) Which industry sectors did these agreements cover?
- automotive industry
 - construction industry
 - chemical industry
- 45) What form of compensation was received?
- Lump-sum payment
 - o Average amount: 25.000 EUR
 - Royalty
 - o Amount:
 - Percentage of post-tax income: 8 %
 - Percentage of revenue:%
 - Other:
- 46) What portion of the above amount goes to the researcher(s)?
- around 35%
- 47) If there were stalled negotiations on commercialization, what was the reason?
- The negotiation was trouble-free
 - Other: negotiations on royalties

Startups

- 84) Are there university startup teams? If yes, who are they, and what achievements have they made?
- HeatVentors - Intelligent Thermal Battery
 - Rollin - eRollers
 - Respray - refillable deodorant bottle
- 85) How much space (m³) is available for university startups?
- around 200 m³
- 86) What kind of support do university startups receive?
- the support from the BME Startup, Spinoff Studio
- 87) What competitions and events have been organised for startups?
- Danube Cup,
 - AI Pitch Competition
 - MNB HIH Cross-university Startup Competition
- 88) Are there any joint startup events or programmes with other universities? (If yes, please, tell us more about this!)

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- Danube Cup,
- MNB HIH Cross-university Startup Competition

NEW IDEAS

- 37) Would you request establishing an expert team within EELISA to advise on license fees and pricing? (please give reasons also)
- Yes, because I think there is a need for a team that is independent of universities and able to negotiate effectively with global industrial partners.
 - No, because...
- 38) Have you experienced aggressive or exploitative tendencies in seeking IP rights from large companies?
Yes, they imagine that because they are the market leaders, they can give whatever cheap price they want and the university will give the intellectual property.
- 39) Is there entrepreneurial knowledge training at the university? If yes, in what form? What are its characteristics? How many students participate?
Yes:
- Innovative start-up course 327 students
 - Start-up management (in Hungarian and in English) 66 students
- 40) How does the university handle the situation of Ph.D. students employed by industrial partners through some grant? Who owns the IP rights generated during the grant? Does the university receive compensation in this case?
- The Cooperative Doctoral Programme is run within a framework set by a ministry.
The rights situation is adapted to where the Phd student creates the intellectual property.
- 89) What additional support could be provided to encourage students, including Ph.D. students, to open up to the industry rather than becoming employees of large corporations while maintaining an academic career?
- Phd research topics should also be evaluated in terms of their usefulness.
And students who develop in marketable areas should be encouraged to develop not only the research result but also the marketable product, with the necessary team.
- 90) In your experience, what skills are essential for a successful industrial and entrepreneurial career? (Free text)
- openness,
 - cooperation,
 - market knowledge,
 - innovation,
 - perseverance,

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- creativity

- 91) Where and in what training format can these skills be acquired at the university? (Free text)
- 92) Does the university offer self-awareness development and communication training, facilitated by psychologists, to support career building?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 93) Does the university provide non-violent/assertive communication training that students can choose?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 94) Does the university have a specialist responsible for product development collaborating with TTO?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 95) Is there a professional at the university, who supports startup, spinoff teams with team-building and mediation?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)
- 96) Is there a dedicated staff (e.g., administrator, accountant, lawyer, project manager) at the university supporting researchers practically during the transformation of inventions into products?
- Yes
 - No, but there is a demand
 - No
 - Other: _____ (Free text)

„ERASMUS for Startappers”

- 49) Do you consider it important to have a mixed composition of startup teams (education, personality, etc.)? Why?

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Yes, mixed teams mean diversity and a wider range of knowledge

50) Do you think students can have traits that are typical of a particular culture (e.g. precise like Germans, generous like Italians, etc.)? Why?

Yes, differences in traditions and child-rearing can have such consequences.

51) Do you think it would be useful to allow students interested in innovation to apply for 1-year scholarships abroad, similar to ERASMUS?

Yes

52) Would your university welcome a foreign startupper (who is also a university student) for teamwork?

Yes

53) What would be your preferences?

- a. - „idea guy/girl” without a team
- b. - member looking for a project
- c. - both

54) Do you see a greater opportunity in 1-year fellowships and/or in idea competitions organized in different countries where the winning team(s) can be supported in longer-term collaboration? Why?

If a team is working properly on a project, it will be clear within 1 year whether it is worth continuing

55) Would you support startup summer camps (min. 2 weeks) in cooperation with host universities?

Yes, for sure.

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